

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 5: Experimentation module

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Abstract

This tutorial discusses the Experimentation module. It showcases the module's general capabilities and provides concrete examples of using it in practice.

Keywords: JECDM, experimentation, comparative analysis, experimental verification

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1. Introduction

The *Experimentation* module is a flexible tool that can assist researchers in effectively conducting experiments. It is primarily designed to be coupled with (interactive) evolutionary (multi-objective) algorithms (e.g., NSGA-III, IEMO/D), but with a little dose of creativity, it can be adapted to other classes of optimizers. Overall, its main features are as follows:

- The module allows designing experimental setups – even concerning massive experiments – relatively quickly.
- The processing imposed by the experimentation tool is efficient both in terms of computational and memory complexity. To use its full potential, however, executing the experimentation process on a PC equipped with a significant number of physical cores is recommended. The reason is that the tool supports parallelization on the so-called trial level, i.e., when repeating executions of a method in order to obtain credible results.

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- The tool can be customized to a large extent. It includes adjusting some internal/technical parameters (e.g., the parallelization level), creating custom experimental scenarios, or adjusting processes responsible for creating result files.

The remaining part of this document provides first the fundamental concepts related to this module, allowing the reader to understand it better. Then, complex use cases are presented to showcase how to use the module in practice.

2. Understanding fundamental concepts

This section discusses selected fundamental concepts related to the experimentation module to give the reader better insight.

2.1. The three-level structure

The experimentation is divided into three layers (also called levels): **global**, **scenario**, and **trial**. It concerns both data and processing. The layers and their general relationships are illustrated in Figure 1. From the data handling perspective, the module introduces three associated classes (and two supportive ones; see the *container* package in the *Experimentation* module):

1. *GlobalDataContainer* (linked to the global level; *container.global* package),
2. *ScenarioDataContainer* and associated *ScenarioDataContainerFactory* (linked to the scenario level; *container.scenario* package),
3. *TrialDataContainer* and associated *TrialDataContainerFactory* (linked to the trial level; *trial.scenario* package).

These data containers are essentially everything that needs to be tuned by the user to establish a complete experimental setup.

The global, scenario, and trial levels (or data containers) can be briefly characterized as follows:

Global level. The global level concerns the general, top-level data (and processing). Establishing this level involves providing information such as the path to the main folder where the results will be stored or the number of threads involved in computations. Overall, this data is considered common (and read-only) for all tasks that will be executed. However, the central – most fundamental – parameterization that must be established globally is determining so-called **experimental scenarios**. One scenario involves employing one method for solving some particular optimization problem.

The experimental scenarios must be defined and instantiated. The former is done globally, while the scenario initialization will be executed at lower levels. Defining scenarios in *GlobalDataContainer* is straightforward. It is assumed that several properties can characterize a scenario, and their names are called in the module **scenario keys** (string data type). For instance, two such keys are specified in the example in Figure 1: *ALGORITHM* and *PROBLEM*. Simply speaking, such a parameterization of the global level implies that each scenario can differ given the algorithm employed and the problem to be tackled.

Naturally, the user can define any properties they want as long as they will be handled at scenario/trial levels (and as long as they satisfy some standardization requirements, which will be discussed later).

Apart from keys, their (i.e., properties) values must be specified as well (string data type). In Figure 1, each key is associated with two values (however, these numbers may differ, of course). E.g., *ALGORITHM* is linked with *NSGA* and *NSGAI*, while *problem* is associated with *DTLZ1* and *DTLZ2*. As with the keys, the user may define any values they want as long as they will be handled later and follow some format requirements.

The system utilizes the scenario keys and values provided by the user to construct a series of experimental scenarios, which can be considered a Cartesian product of combining all specified values for each key. In Figure 1, for instance, the system can construct up to four scenarios given the key and values provided:

- *ALGORITHM* = *NSGA* and *PROBLEM* = *DTLZ1*,
- *ALGORITHM* = *NSGA* and *PROBLEM* = *DTLZ2*,
- *ALGORITHM* = *NSGAI* and *PROBLEM* = *DTLZ1*,
- *ALGORITHM* = *NSGAI* and *PROBLEM* = *DTLZ2*.

Naturally, the user can disable some unwanted scenarios produced in this way by specifying so-called disabling conditions (which will be discussed later). Overall, the scenarios will be performed sequentially (one by one) during the experiment execution.

Scenario level. One scenario level concerns one element of a Cartesian product that resulted from combining all scenario key-values. E.g., as already explained, there are four such elements in Figure 1. As with the global level, the user will have to parameterize the *ScenarioDataContainer* class – but not explicitly (which was the case for the *GlobalDataContainer*). Instead of creating *ScenarioDataContainer*, the user will be requested to instantiate its associated factory-like class: *ScenarioDataContainerFactory*. The rationale is that although there is one *GlobalDataContainer* for the whole experimentation (therefore, it can be instantiated explicitly), the scenario-related container can be parameterized depending on which scenario is being processed currently (which means that constant, fixed parameterization is pointless).

Overall, the experimentation processing task utilizes the *ScenarioDataContainerFactory* to create *ScenarioDataContainer* that will be associated with a concrete scenario being processed. The factory allows setting a variety of data relevant to evolutionary multi-objective optimization and making measurements regarding the algorithm’s performance. For instance (the containers will be discussed in detail later), the user may supply the container with the limit for the number of generations the scenario’s algorithm will be run for. This limit can be fixed (which means it will be the same for all scenarios to be executed) or specified conditionally, depending on which scenario is currently being solved. For example, the number of generations may be a key defined at the global level (key = “GENERATIONS”), and its values can be, e.g., “100”, “200”, and “300”. When setting the factory object, the user can derive the

Figure 1: The three-level structure

relevant key’s value (get value for key = “GENERATION”) for the processed scenario.

Trial level. A scenario is supposed to test one algorithm given some specific conditions. However, executing a method involving a random factor – e.g., an evolutionary algorithm once is not enough to derive credible conclusions. Therefore, the module allows executing the tested methods a desired number of times (e.g., 100). These runs are done at the **trial level**, i.e., each trial is one test run.

As with the scenario level, the trial level also operates on two data-related classes: *TrialDataContainer* that is implicitly parameterized via its factory counterpart – *TrialDataContainerFactory*. The two essential data elements that need to be supplied via the factory are *EA* and *Runner* initializers. The first one is, naturally, the optimizer, while the latter is the object maintaining its execution.

Worth highlighting is the fact that the test runs are executed as threads dispatched to a dedicated thread pool of a size that the user can specify. It means that many of the test runs within one scenario may be executed simultaneously, speeding up the overall execution time significantly. Naturally, the parallelization level is bounded by the number of physical PC cores on which the experiments are conducted. Note that executing the following scenario will not start until all test runs are completed. It is ensured by imposing synchronization barriers on processing.

2.2. Experiment performer and summarizers

Experiment performer and summarizers (executors) are objects responsible for – naturally – executing the processing specified by the user containers (global/scenario/trial). The initial release of JECMD introduces three fundamental such summarizers that can be established by the user and used (see executor package):

- *ExperimentPerformer* – executes the experimentation task.

- *ScenariosSummarizer* – summarizes the results at the scenario level.
- *CrossSummarizer* – conducts highest-level cross-examination/validation/etc.

When talking about designing and running an experiment, the document will be referring to *ExperimentPerformer*. The latter two executors are responsible for post processing the already obtained result data, and they will be introduced later. As for now, the reader should understand that – to conduct the experiment – they first have to instantiate all three containers (factories) and use them within *ExperimentPerformer*.

The *ExperimentPerformer* class per-se will not be explicitly discussed – it does not have a dedication section. The rationale is that its operation is highly entwined with how the data containers are structured and parameterized. Therefore, the processing will be discussed simultaneously when showcasing the data containers in the following sections. Overall, it is imperative to understand that the final result of *ExperimentPerformer* is a series of results per-trial binary files that will be stored in relevant per-scenario folders in the main catalog specified by the user.

The rationale for using binary files is that the total number of per-trial results may be enormous in real-world uses. Thus, the results have to be stored in a compact and efficient for processing files. These requirements are satisfied by binaries. Additionally, one rarely wishes to examine such lower-level results. Instead, they often want to produce summary-like results. It can be accomplished by the two above-mentioned extra executors: *ScenariosSummarizer* and *CrossSummarizer* – that will be discussed in the later parts of this document. As for now, the user must understand that these executors (i) operate on the same data containers designed for *ExperimentPerformer* and (ii) on the binary files created by it. Overall, the user has to create the containers first. Then, they can be used by various executors to

create the raw data (binaries) or summary-like result files.

Some very general characteristics of the processing imposed by *ExperimentPerformer* (and its summarizing counterparts) are as follows:

On memory management. The system was developed to be “light”. Since the scenarios are executed sequentially, the systems keep their overall signatures at the global level only. When processing a single scenario, only then is the respective data container created (but it also may be light). It is the same for the trial level. The dispatched threads initially contain only data that is relevant for creating a proper data container. The container itself is, however, created only when the thread is run (so not all *TrialDataContainers* are created immediately, but they are established on demand when the respective thread is started). Naturally, the greater the number of physical cores and the parallelization level set, the more such containers will be kept in the memory simultaneously. Overall, most of the memory consumed by the executor at some specific time is related primarily to the currently processed trials.

On exception handling. A primitive yet sufficient exception-handling system was implemented for this module. It was designed to be (i) informative and (ii) able to turn off processing only of error-relevant parts, permitting the remaining processes to be executed without interfering. Overall, three error-related cases are possible, related to at which level the error occurred:

- Trial level: only the trial task that caused the error is terminated. The remaining trials proceed normally (and scenarios as well). It may happen when, e.g., creating the *TrialDataContainer* (and validating) using *TrialDataContainerFactory* or when running the algorithm.
- Scenario level: executing the scenario is invalidated (the trial threads are not dispatched). It can happen when creating (and validating) the *ScenarioDataContainer* using *ScenarioDataContainerFactory*. The other scenarios are not affected by the error caused by this scenario.
- Global level: this may happen during data validation in *GlobalDataContainer*. The experimentation is prematurely terminated if the exception is triggered (no scenarios are executed).

On the report-like outputs. As with the *DecisionSupportSystem*, the experimentation tool provides reports on its execution using report-like classes. These are filled at all three levels (i.e., per trial, scenario, or global reports) and collected (when requested), allowing the user to get a comprehensive insight into the experimentation process.

2.3. Creating GlobalDataContainer

As with other major framework’s components, the parameterization of *GlobalDataContainer* is done via its inner *Params* class. This section discusses set-by-step its most essential fields, including how to set them to establish a desired experimentation setup. Note that some of the less fundamental fields

are skipped for brevity - the reader should feel free to inspect them on their own. Additionally, as already explained, one instance *GlobalDataContainer* is supposed to be shared among different executors (e.g., *CrossSummarizer*). The fields relevant only to non-*ExperimentPerformer* classes will also be skipped as they will have no meaning. The primary focus is to showcase how to create the containers (factories) and the *ExperimentPerformer* (further sections) now. The following subsections showcase the selected, most fundamental parameterization means. They are discussed under the assumption that the params container is established as shown in Listing 1. **Additional note:** The validity of most of these fields will be checked when instantiating the container or during the relevant processing steps. For instance, the system will throw an exception and stop processing if it is not possible to create a specified main folder for results.

Listing 1: Creating GlobalDataContainer.Params object

```
// Create the params container:
GlobalDataContainer.Params pGDC = new
GlobalDataContainer.Params();
```

2.3.1. Specifying the main path

Listing 1 showcases how to specify the main path for the folder in which the result of the experimentation will be stored. In this example, the path is *E:\results*.

Listing 2: Establishing the main path

```
// Specify the main path for the folder
where the results will be stored:
pGDC._mainPath = "E:\\results";
```

2.3.2. Defining the scenarios

Defining the experimental scenarios is straightforward. It can be done by suitably setting the “*String [] _scenarioKeys*” and “*String [] _scenarioValues*” fields. Listing 3 presents how to define the same scenarios as shown in Figure 1.

Listing 3: Defining the scenarios

```
// Defined scenario keys (labels/
definitions); note that the key/values
will be standardized (check the JavaDoc)
pGDC._scenarioKeys = new String[]{"
Algorithm", "Problem"};
// Define scenario values (1:1 mapping with
keys):
pGDC._scenarioValues = new String[][]{"
NSGA", "NSGAI"}, {"DTLZ1", "DTLZ2"};
```

Important note: The input labels will be first transformed by the system into an uppercase format for the sake of standardization (so, e.g., “nsga” = “NSGA”). Second, only [A-Z], [a-z], and [0-9] characters are allowed by default. The reason is that these labels will be used when creating various subfolders and result files, and this way, the risk of using forbidden characters when creating a folder/file is minimized. Note that, however,

extra allowed characters can be specified via the “*Character [] _extraAllowedCharacters*” field. It is supplied with the “_” character by default, making it also available.

Special keys: note that some keys are considered “special.” Their use may imply some shortcuts in processing – some fields for lower-level containers may be filled automatically. Their list is provided in *scenario.Keys* enum (“PROBLEM”, “ALGORITHM”, “OBJECTIVES”, and “GENERATIONS”). Their primary purpose is to allow for quick value (or concrete object) retrieval at lower levels. For instance, the *Scenario* class (scenario’s signature) has such methods as “*getObjectives*” (and similar), which return the number of objectives associated with the “OBJECTIVES” key in the scenario being currently processed (or null, if there is no such a key). Generally, the user should not fear using these keys and reinterpreting them if needed.

Lastly, the results of the scenarios resulting from the provided keys and values will be stored in corresponding folders (stored in the main folder), whose names will be composed of key-value segments. Specifically, the format used can be presented as: “KEY1_VALUE1_KEY2_VALUE2_ ..._KEYn_VALUEn”, where *n* denotes the number of keys, and VALUE_{*i*} is the *i*-th key’s value appointed to the scenario. For example, one of the four folders created by the setting defined in Listing 3 can be “ALGORITHM_NSGA_PROBLEM_DTLZ2”.

Important note: The order of the keys will be, by default as provided by the “*String [] _scenarioKeys*” field, with the proviso that the special keys have non-standard ordering: if “PROBLEM” is used it will be placed ordered first; if “OBJECTIVES” is used, it will be first or just behind “PROBLEM; similarly “GENERATIONS” follows the former two; the “ALGORITHM” key – if used – will be placed last. However, the ordering priority can be altered via the “*int[] _keyValuesOrder*” field.

2.3.3. Setting scenario disabling conditions

By default, the Cartesian product of all specified keys and their values will be produced, and each element will serve as one experimental scenario. However, the user may be willing to narrow this – potentially huge – scenario set as some of the resulting experiments may have no sense or relevance (to the user). It can be achieved with the assistance of the “*ScenarioDisablingConditions[] _scenarioDisablingConditions*” field. In short, a specific scenario will be excluded from processing if it satisfies at least one of the provided “scenario disabling conditions”. A single condition is a subset of keys and their selected values. A condition is satisfied if all the values of all its selected keys are set in the same way in the scenario. As for example, consider the following keys and values: *KEY1*: [V11, V12, V12], *KEY2*: [V21, V22], and *KEY3*: [V31, V32, V33]. Overall, it would produce $3 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 = 18$ unique scenarios. Imagine, however, that the user wishes to exclude all scenarios that simultaneously have *KEY1 = V11 and KEY2 = V22* (the first condition), or (and) *KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V31* (the second condition). Consequently, the number of scenarios to be processed will drop from 18 to 12, i.e., only the below scenarios do not satisfy at least one of these disabling conditions:

1. *KEY1 = V11 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V31*
2. *KEY1 = V11 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V32*
3. *KEY1 = V11 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V33*
4. *KEY1 = V11 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V31*
5. *KEY1 = V11 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V32*
6. *KEY1 = V11 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V33*
7. *KEY1 = V12 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V31*
8. *KEY1 = V12 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V32*
9. *KEY1 = V12 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V33*
10. *KEY1 = V12 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V31*
11. *KEY1 = V12 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V32*
12. *KEY1 = V12 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V33*
13. *KEY1 = V13 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V31*
14. *KEY1 = V13 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V32*
15. *KEY1 = V13 and KEY2 = V21 and KEY3 = V33*
16. *KEY1 = V13 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V31*
17. *KEY1 = V13 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V32*
18. *KEY1 = V13 and KEY2 = V22 and KEY3 = V33*

The above can be accomplished by using the code presented in Listing 4.

Listing 4: Defining the scenario disabling conditions

```
pGDC._scenarioKeys = new String[]{"KEY1", "KEY2", "KEY3"};
pGDC._scenarioValues = new String[][]{{"V11", "V12", "V13"}, {"V21", "V22", "V23"}, {"V31", "V32", "V33"}};
pGDC._scenarioDisablingConditions = new ScenarioDisablingConditions[]{
    // Elements are mapped 1:1
    new ScenarioDisablingConditions(new String[]{"KEY1", "KEY2"}, new String[]{"V11", "V22"}),
    new ScenarioDisablingConditions(new String[]{"KEY2", "KEY3"}, new String[]{"V21", "V31"})
};
```

2.3.4. Setting the number of test runs

Defining the number of test runs to be performed in each scenario is straightforward – see Listing 5. **Important note:** the test runs are not anonymous. Each is assigned a trial ID, which is a simple integer. The test runs are assigned the IDs starting from 0. Hence, the *IDs* are 0, 1, ..., 99 if the number of test runs is set to 100. This way, if needed, the per-trial data (e.g., an algorithm) can be parameterized **conditionally on the assigned trial ID**. Furthermore, the individual, i.e., per-trial results, will be stored in separate files with the “_N” suffix, where *N* stands for the trial ID. Finally, it is worth highlighting that the number of test runs to be executed per scenario is considered constant throughout all experimental setups.

Listing 5: Defining the number of test runs

```
// No. trials to be performed for each
// scenario (IDs = 0, 1, ..., 99)
pGDC._noTrials = 100;
```

```

[28.11.2024 16:43:44:172]: Monitor log =====
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:172]: Scenario = PROBLEML_DTLZ3_OBJECTIVES_4_ALGORITHM_NSGAIII
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 40, millis = 13]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: The total number of trials = 100
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: The number of awaiting trials = 40
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: The number of trials being processed = 20
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: The number of finished trials = 40
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: The number of trials terminated due to exception = 0
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: The states of trials being currently processed:
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 40 Generation = [1385/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:32:457] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 11, millis = 714]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 41 Generation = [1175/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:34:482] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 9, millis = 689]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 42 Generation = [1212/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:34:542] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 9, millis = 629]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 43 Generation = [1224/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:34:644] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 9, millis = 527]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 44 Generation = [1067/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:35:106] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 9, millis = 65]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 45 Generation = [1074/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:35:301] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 8, millis = 870]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 46 Generation = [1016/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:35:778] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 8, millis = 393]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 47 Generation = [1072/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:35:944] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 8, millis = 227]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 48 Generation = [959/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:36:414] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 7, millis = 757]
[28.11.2024 16:43:44:173]: Trial = 49 Generation = [917/1750] Processing started = [28.11.2024 16:43:36:582] Processing for = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 7, millis = 582]

```

Figure 2: Example log produced by the monitor thread

2.3.5. Setting trial disabling conditions

As with the scenarios, the user may also specify the trial disabling conditions. As the name suggests, they will dictate which trials should be excluded from processing (the verification is based on checking trial IDs). It may be helpful when splitting the calculations on different machines. E.g., one may have two PCs on which the experiment could be performed. Assuming that both machines are of similar class and 100 test runs are to be performed per scenario, a reasonable split could be: run trials with IDs 0-49 on the first PC while letting the remaining trials, i.e., 50-99, be processed on the second PC. After the calculations are done, the resulting experiment folders could be merged (no conflicts are expected). What is more, the module provides a simple parser for the arguments that can be passed to *ExperimentPerformer*. In short, the trial (and scenario) disabling conditions can be specified via the console and supplied to the generated JAR file. However, providing them via the command will be discussed later in Section 2.6.1. Finally, a source code that would force utilizing only 0-49 trials (from 100 ones) is presented in Listing 6.

Listing 6: Excluding specific trials from processing

```

pGDC._noTrials = 100;
pGDC._trialDisablingConditions = new
    TrialDisablingConditions(pGDC._noTrials)
;
pGDC._trialDisablingConditions.
    disableTrials(50, 99);

```

2.3.6. Setting the number of threads

The user may specify the thread pool size on which all the per-scenario threads will be executed. This number should be set based on (i) the hardware specification and (ii) the number of test runs to be performed. Regarding (i), the number of threads is naturally limited by the number of physical cores. Further, it is also recommended to set this number in a way that makes the number of test runs divisible by it. For instance, if the number of test runs is 100, the number of threads could be 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 25, 50, or 100. The rationale for this is the fact that evolutionary algorithms often complete calculations in a similar time in different test runs (assuming, of course, constant

limit for the number of generations, etc.) Consequently, such parameterization is expected to shorten the total experimentation time most significantly, e.g., if the number of test runs is 100 and the number of threads is 20, one may expect around 5 times quicker completion time (naturally, it depends on various factors and this is just an approximation). Listing 7 showcases how to set the thread pool size to 20.

Listing 7: Specifying the thread pool size

```

// Split processing into threads (Important
    note: use value that is similar to user
    's no. physical cores,
// and gives no. trials % no. threads == 0)
pGDC._noThreads = 20;

```

2.3.7. Using the monitor thread

It may take a long time before all test runs are completed for a scenario. To get insight into “what is currently going on,” a so-called monitor thread may be dispatched along the trial threads. The monitor is responsible for periodically reporting the current processing state as a console output. Turning the monitor thread on (it is on by default) and specifying its interval for reporting (10 s by default) is straightforward and is presented in Listing 8. Figure 2 illustrates the most relevant snippet of an example such log. The report provides some general feedback, e.g., on how many trials have been successfully (or not) completed so far. It also reports the current state of the trials being processed (current generation, starting time, and processing time). Note that the monitor does not impose any lock when reading the data (asynchronous read). Hence, the report may be inconsistent, but to a minor degree, and without affecting the actual usability of this tool.

Listing 8: Parameterizing the monitor thread

```

// Monitor thread = reports the progress on
    executing a scenario. The report will
    be printed into the console
// after each provided ms (reporting
    interval).
pGDC._useMonitorThread = true; // turn on (
    true by default)

```

```
pGDC._monitorReportingInterval = 1000; //
    set to 1000 ms
```

2.3.8. Providing additional data via associative arrays

The global data container can additionally be supplied with various objects maintained by associative arrays. The keys they use are custom strings. As for the values, four data types (and, thus, maps) are available: *Integer*, *Double*, *String*, and the *Object*. The maps can be passed via the params container and will be accessible at lower processing levels (e.g., scenario) from the available global data container. They may be helpful when, e.g., supplying the experimentation with some custom, problem-specific data containers (which can be fixed throughout experimentation). Listing 9 showcases how to provide the container with four example objects of different types.

Listing 9: Providing additional data via maps

```
pGDC._mapObject = new HashMap<>();
pGDC._mapObject.put("SOME_OBJECT", new
    Range(0.0d, 1.0d));
pGDC._mapInteger = new HashMap<>();
pGDC._mapInteger.put("SOME_INTEGER", 10);
pGDC._mapDouble = new HashMap<>();
pGDC._mapDouble.put("SOME_DOUBLE", 10.0d);
pGDC._mapString = new HashMap<>();
pGDC._mapString.put("SOME_STRING", "TEST");
```

2.3.9. On the random number generator

A random number generator is central to metaheuristics, e.g., evolutionary algorithms. Setting it properly is required to conduct the experiments correctly. This module assumes that each *TrialDataContainer* will receive a unique random number generator upon creation. This object (unique to each trial) is supposed to be used when, e.g., instantiating the evolutionary algorithm (creating own generators during the algorithm creation is not recommended). The generators are requested from *GlobalDataContainer* using *IRandom requestRandomNumberGenerator()* method (the calls are synchronous). The container has an internal counter incremented each time the generator is requested, and the actual object creation is delegated to a dedicated initializer – *IRandomNumberGeneratorInitializer* (see *container.global.initializers* package). The method called is *IRandom getRNG(int currentCounterValue)*. The implementation used by *GlobalDataContainer* by default is *DefaultRandomNumberGeneratorInitializer*, and it creates a Mersenne Twister generator (64-bit) with a seed being set as imposed by the passed counter. This way, each trial thread will receive a generator with a different, non-colliding seed. Since the generator used is designed to produce uncorrelated outcomes given different seeds, the overall generator-supply process can be deemed methodologically correct. However, if needed, one can create own implementation of *IRandomNumberGeneratorInitializer* and pass it to the *GlobalDataContainer* via its params container (“_RNGI” field).

2.4. Creating ScenarioDataContainerFactory

During experiment execution, each scenario, at the beginning of its processing, will be assigned a signature: *Scenario* object (see *scenario* package). The *Scenario* object contains various fields that determine completely the concrete scenario being processed (e.g., values linked to the keys). Then, the respective *ScenarioDataContainer* instance will be created. Since each scenario can have a differently parameterized such container, they are not intended to be pre-constructed by the user and supplied along with the parameterization of the *GlobalDataContainer* when creating the *ExperimentPerformer*. Instead, the user must create its factory-like counterpart: *ScenarioDataContainerFactory* class (see *container.scenario* package). Its central method is *AbstractScenarioDataContainer getInstance(AbstractGlobalDataContainer GDC, Scenario scenario, Validator validator)* that the executor calls to create an actual container. Note that the global data container and the scenario’s signature are passed via the input (along with an auxiliary validator), which gives the possibility to parameterize the construction process conditionally.

Note that the “*getInstance*” method should not be overwritten, etc. As usual, the factory’s parameterization should be done via its params container. The following subsections cover selected central fields that are most relevant to the proper execution of the *ExperimentPerformer*.

Before proceeding, it is also worth highlighting that the data specified at the higher level should be considered constant for the processing done at lower levels. For example, the scenario/trial processing should not affect the main path maintained by the global data container (which is apparent). Similarly, trial processing is not allowed to change data established at both higher levels (e.g., the limit for the number of generations).

Finally, let assume that the params container for *ScenarioDataContainerFactory* is created as presented in Listing 10.

Listing 10: Creating ScenarioDataContainerFactory.Params object

```
// Create the params container:
ScenarioDataContainerFactory.Params pSDCF =
    new ScenarioDataContainerFactory.Params
    ();
```

2.4.1. Setting the limit for the number of generations

The limit for the number of generations should be specified at the scenario level. As already explained, the lower level (trial) must then respect this setting (individual trials – within one scenario – cannot change this limit). Overall, the limit can be set in two ways (and this will be often the case for other parameters as well): **fixed or conditional**.

Setting a fixed number of generations is straightforward and is presented in Listing 11 (where the limit is set to 500). This setting implies using the same limit for all scenarios involved in experimentations. During the creation of the scenario data container, the factory object will pass this specified limit to the container being constructed.

Listing 11: Setting a fixed limit for the number of generations

```
pSDCF._generations = 500;
```

The truth is that the fixed number of generations is not passed to the container alone. Additionally, an auxiliary *INumberOfGenerationsInitializer* object (see *container.scenario.initializers* package) is also passed (its custom implementation can be supplied via the factory’s params container). When instantiated, the scenario data container questions the initializer on how to set the generation limit. By default, a *DefaultNumberOfGenerationsInitializer* is used, which immediately returns the fixed number of generations specified by the user. However, the *INumberOfGenerationsInitializer* interface has just one straightforward method signature, which expects returning the limit given the scenario params container – which makes a variety of the data on the scenario (and the global level) available. Therefore, one may implement this interface (even as a lambda expression) and pass it via the factory’s params container to customize the processing. For example, Listing 12 exemplifies how to conditionally set the limit based on the scenario’s characteristic in two ways (derived from key and value: the key = “GENERATIONS”, while its values specify the limits; or by using the shortcut). Naturally, the example assumes that the user specified the respective key (“GENERATIONS”) and reasonably set their values (non-negative integers represented as string) at the global level.

Listing 12: Conditionally setting the limit for the number of generations

```
pSDCF._numberOfGenerationsInitializer = p
-> {
  // p = scenario's params container filled
  // by the experiment executor
  // _scenario: scenario object (provides
  // data on the scenario being processed;
  // particularly on key-values)
  // keyValuesMap = allows retrieving
  // current scenario value for a specified
  // key (note that using keyValues
  // is faster, but may be prone to errors
  // due to the fact that GDC may alter the
  // orders in which keys are stored).
  // get = Value object; next getValue
  // gives its string representation
  return Integer.parseInt(p._scenario.
    getKeyValuesMap().get("GENERATIONS").
    getValue());
  // Shortcut can also be used for "
  // GENERATIONS":
  //return p._scenario.getGenerations();
};
```

2.4.2. Setting the number of steady-state repeats

The number of steady-state repeats for the algorithm to be investigated in the scenario can be set in the same way as the number of generations, i.e., by providing a fixed value (“*pSDCF.steadyStateRepeats = 1*”) or by implementing respective initializer: *INumberOfSteadyStateRepeatsInitializer*. The interface is similar to the one dedicated to the generation

limit. However, note that the number of steady-state repeats is rather an algorithm-related concept (and depends on its parameterization). Therefore, no shortcuts are introduced here.

2.4.3. Setting the number of objectives

Setting the number of objectives follows the already known pattern: setting a fixed value (“*pSDCF.objectives = 1*”) or using a dedicated initializer (*INumberOfObjectivesInitializer*). Assume that the user specified the key = “OBJECTIVES” and its values: “2”, “3”, “4”, “5”. Conditional parameterization of the number of objectives for the scenario can be done as shown in Listing 13.

Listing 13: Conditionally setting the number of objectives

```
pSDCF._numberOfObjectivesInitializer = p ->
{
  //return Integer.parseInt(p._scenario.
  //getKeyValuesMap().get("OBJECTIVES").
  //getValue());
  return p._scenario.getObjectives();
};
```

2.4.4. Setting the performance indicators

The evolutionary algorithm to be run must be assessed (potentially many times at the trial level). The evaluation is done via object(s) implementing *IIndicator* interface (see *indicator* package). The user may specify more than one indicator per scenario, meaning that the method to be tested will be evaluated from different perspectives. Additionally, the indicators can differ between the scenarios. As usual, two parameterization ways are available: fixed (via “*pSDCF.indicators*” field) or conditional (by using a dedicated *IIndicatorsInitializer* initializer).

The initial release provides several indicators that will be presented later. However, the user may wish to create their indicator. For this reason, they will be asked to implement the *IIndicator* interface. Its code is brought in Listing 14 for convenience. Let’s discuss some of its methods.

First, the indicators specified at the scenario level are again factory-like objects (see the “*getInstance*” method). They will be cloned at the trial level (and can be conditionally parameterized given the trial ID). The rationale is that although one semantically consistent indicator can be assumed to be used within one scenario, one may sometimes wish to use its slightly different internal parameterizations in different test runs. For instance, when testing interactive methods, it is common to assume a different model of an artificial decision maker in different test runs. This way, a comprehensive method capability of discovering different relevant parts of the Pareto front can be tested. Hence, although a single measure may be employed to test it on the scenario level, one could use, e.g., different models of an artificial decision maker in different runs to design such an experimental setting. Another rationale is allowing the indicators to maintain individual (per trial) internal data required for calculations. Nonetheless, the implementation of this method will often just involve simple cloning.

Listing 14: Indicator interface

```

/**
 * Interface for classes responsible for
 * assessing the performance of an EA
 * given the current state (population,
 * generation, etc.)
 * Note that the indicators are (by default
 * ) established at the scenario level.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface IIndicator
{
    /**
     * Each indicator must implement this
     * factory-like method. After
     * establishing the indicator at the
     * scenario level,
     * each dispatched trial executor
     * receives a copy. This allows each
     * instance to maintain its own trial-
     * dependent data.
     * Effectively, this method intends to
     * clone the reference object in its
     * initial state.
     *
     * @param scenario scenario being
     * currently processed
     * @param trialID ID of a trial being
     * processed
     * @return new instance (clear,
     * unprocessed) of the indicator
     * @throws TrialException trial-level
     * exception can be thrown and
     * propagated higher
     */
    IIndicator getInstance(Scenario scenario,
        int trialID) throws TrialException;

    /**
     * The main method for performance
     * evaluation.
     *
     * @param ea instance of the evolutionary
     * algorithm to be assessed
     * @return the assessment
     * @throws TrialException the method's
     * signature allows for exception throw
     * (trial level)
     */
    double evaluate(EA ea) throws
        TrialException;

    /**
     * Method for identifying preference
     * direction.
     *
     * @return preference direction (if true,
     * less is preferred; if false, more is
     * preferred)

```

```

 */
    boolean isLessPreferred();

    /**
     * Returns the indicator's name. Note
     * that the name should obey the same
     * naming rules as the titles of the
     * scenarios' keys and values.
     *
     * @return the indicator's name
     */
    String getName();

    [...]
}

```

The central method is obviously here “*double evaluate(EA ea)*”. The executor will employ it to assess the evolutionary algorithm processed in a trial thread. The attained scores are represented using double format. Further, “*boolean isLessPreferred()*” is a complementary method that informs about the preference direction (i.e., *true* means that lesser values are preferred; false otherwise).

Important note: The iteration concept in this module is equivalent to generations, meaning all methods will be evaluated after each generation. **It is the only – and lowest – time unit considered.** It implies that the methods cannot be assessed, e.g., after each steady-state repeat.

Finally, the “*String getName()*” method should return the indicator’s unique identifier (string). It obeys the same rules as the key/values for scenarios (i.e., using an awkward character is forbidden). The rationale is the same – the name will be employed, e.g., in the names of the result files – so it is recommended to use [a-z], [A-Z], [1-9] characters to avoid potential errors. Note that the name will not be transformed into an uppercase (so it is case-sensitive). Further, the names will be validated by the system (e.g., their uniqueness; note that the instantiable classes often allow for surpassing the default indicator’s name to avoid collisions).

Important note: as already explained, the final files produced by *ExperimentPerformer* are per-trial (individual) binary files, and the trial IDs are used as the suffixes: “_ID.bin”. Regarding the prefix, it is the indicator’s name used to make an assessment. For instance, if the indicator’s name is “HV”, the resulting per-trial files will be named “HV_0”, “HV_1”, etc. Each such file will store the double scores attained throughout generations (i.e., from 0 to the generation limit imposed). Additionally, remember that multiple indicators can be employed in the assessment. Consequently, per-scenario’s per-trial results will contain various files combining the indicator’s names (prefixes) and trial IDs (suffixes). For instance, if “HV” and “IGD” indicators are used, there will be “HV_0” and “IGD_0”, “HV_1” and “IGD_1”, etc. files, each dedicated to the assessment done in a specific trial and according to a particular indicator.

2.4.5. Setting data storing interval

The trial thread, when created, instantiates a double matrix that will store algorithm assessments collected throughout all gener-

ations. This matrix associates columns with performance indicators and rows with subsequent generations. However, the matrix can be enormous in more extensive experimental scenarios, implying significant memory consumption. The user is given the possibility to alleviate this issue by limiting the number of rows for this data matrix (limiting its size). Each time the matrix is overflowed, the data is transferred from the memory to relevant result files, and the matrix is cleared at the same time. It allows for reducing memory complexity at the cost of increasing hard drive input operations. The params container provides an auxiliary field that controls this limit: “*dataStoringInterval*”. Listing 15 showcases how to set it to an arbitrary number of 100, which will cause data transfer after every 100 generations.

Listing 15: Setting the data storing interval

```
// The field below can be adjusted to
// balance memory consumption and hard
// drive input operations (default value
// = Integer.MAX_VALUE). Generally, the EA's
// assessment (per trial) is stored in a
// matrix (rows = generations X
// columns = indicators). For the default
// setting, the assessment is completed
// when the algorithm finishes
// processing and only after the data is
// moved from the memory into binary files.
// However, the field below
// steers the maximum number of rows in the
// results matrix. During the algorithm
// execution, if the allowed
// capacity is overflowed, the data is
// flushed to the files, and the matrix is
// cleared. Overall, the smaller
// the interval, the lesser the memory
// consumption, but the disc input
// operations are more frequently executed.
pSDCF._dataStoringInterval = 100;
```

2.4.6. Providing and retrieving additional data via associative arrays

The data provided at the global level via associative arrays can be easily accessed at lower levels. It can be done in various initializer-like objects, which allow the user to customize the processing flow. Specifically, their main methods are supplied with the filled scenario params container, which also provides access to the global data container. Listing 16 shows how one can access this data when establishing the number of generations for a scenario. Note that this example showcases how to access the data, not its particular use. Naturally, it is expected that the elements associated with the provided keys exist (i.e., were specified at the global level).

Listing 16: Retrieving additional data from maps

```
pSDCF._numberOfGenerationsInitializer = p
-> {
    Double d = p._GDC.getDouble("SOME_KEY");
    Integer i = p._GDC.getInteger("SOME_KEY");
};
```

```
String s = p._GDC.getString("SOME_KEY");
Object o = p._GDC.getObject("SOME_KEY");
return p._scenario.getGenerations();
};
```

2.5. Creating TrialDataContainerFactory

TrialDataContainer is responsible for maintaining trial-related data. Its creation is also via its corresponding factory class: *TrialDataContainerFactory*. As with the scenario-level factory, the user can define conditional parameterization of the trial data container via respective initializers. In turn, there are no fixed parameterization ways as it is expected now that (i) fixed-like parameters should be accessible from the scenario level (e.g., the generations limit) and (ii) each trial should be unique. Regarding the latter, the central element of the trial data container is an evolutionary algorithm. The system cannot create just one instance of the method object and share it among all trial threads. Instead, each trial has to create the evolutionary method from scratch – using the parameterization established at higher levels.

Generally, the user can supply three elementary initializers: the problem bundle, evolutionary algorithm, and runner. Of these three, only the second really must be specified. As for the first and the third, their default implementations (set in the default factory params container) are sufficient for most applications. For instance, the *DefaultProblemBundleInitializer* checks if a special key “PROBLEM” is used in scenario definitions. If so, it then examines whether the associated value matches some pre-defined problem definitions – “DTLZ1”-“DTLZ7” and “WFG1”-“WFG9” are available in the initial release. If the value matches one of them, the respective *AbstractProblemBundle* object is constructed (the problem bundles were already discussed in previous tutorial documents) and stored as an accessible field in the constructed trial data container params (note that, depending on the problem, it may require retrieving the number of objectives from the scenario level; therefore the “OBJECTIVES” key may also need to be specified). The problem bundle provides useful data for properly instantiating the evolutionary algorithm, e.g., criteria definitions or normalization functions. As for the runner, *DefaultRunnerInitializer* creates the runner object that the trial thread will use to execute the evolutionary process. Note that the default initialization takes into account the number of steady-state repeats (set at the scenario level) and the instance of the evolutionary algorithm (set at the trial level). Naturally, the runner is not supplied with visualization.

Important note note that the three components mentioned above, i.e., the problem bundle, evolutionary algorithm, and the runner, are instantiated at the same level, and their parameterizations are interrelated (e.g., initializing the runner requires creating the algorithm first). Therefore, the relevant initializers are executed in a precise order during the processing. Specifically, the optional problem bundle is constructed first. Next, the evolutionary method can be instantiated and may use the already created bundle (if it was created). Lastly, the runner employing the just-created algorithm can be instantiated. Nonetheless, it

is worth remembering that creating just the evolutionary algorithm will often be sufficient, and there will be no need to adjust the remaining two components.

2.5.1. Creating per-trial instance of the evolutionary algorithm

Listing 17 showcases an example custom initializer that creates an instance of NSGA-II tuned to solve a problem that should be accessible from the problem bundle (if not, the exception is thrown). Naturally, the custom implementation may be more flexible, e.g., take into account which algorithm should be instantiated (e.g., by setting a relevant scenario key definition like “ALGORITHM” and its relevant values, e.g., “NSGAI” and “MOEAD”). It is up to the user to take control over the initialization, given the specific conditions (scenario or global). **Important note:** The signature of the central initializer’s method breaks the pattern of a single-element input. Here, apart from the params container, a dedicated random generator is passed, and the evolutionary algorithm should employ it (it is also available via the params container, but this additional input plays the role of a reminder).

Listing 17: Conditional creation of evolutionary algorithm

```
// Creating EA should be conditional:
pTDCF._eaInitializer = (R1, p) -> {
    if (!(p._problemBundle instanceof
        AbstractMOOProblemBundle bundle))
        throw new TrialException("Problem
            bundle is not available", null, p.
                _SDC.getScenario(), p._trialID);
    return NSGAI.getNSGAI(p._trialID, false
        , 100, R1, bundle);
};
```

2.6. Creating ExperimentPerformer

ExperimentPerformer is the primary class for conducting the experiments. The overall experimental design is modeled – from the data perspective – via *GlobalDataContainer*, *ScenarioDataContainerFactory*, and *TrialDataContainerFactory*. In turn, *ExperimentPerformer* conducts the processing oriented on producing the results, and, for this purpose, it employs these three containers (factories).

Listing 18 brings the most relevant code snippets of the *ExperimentPerformer* class for convenience. As expected, it has an inner *Params* class as a parameterization means. Its core fields are the data containers (factories). The user may also set some auxiliary parameters primarily related to reporting. For instance, the “*notify*” flag can be false to turn off printing logs into the console. The remaining parameters are left to the reader for inspection.

Consider also the “*execute*” method that can be called to start processing. First, its return type is *Summary*. It is a report-like class that plays a similar role to *Report/Result* classes in the *DecisionSupport* module – it provides an overview of the experimentation process. It includes processing time, the number of successfully completed scenarios, the number of scenarios that were prematurely terminated due to an exception, and many more.

Moreover, the *execute()* method directly delegates the processing to *execute(String[] args)*. The input here is some additional arguments that can be passed to the console to parameterize processing accordingly. This matter will be discussed in the following section.

Listing 18: ExperimentPerformer class

```
/**
 * The main executor class (responsible for
 *   conducting the experiments).
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class ExperimentPerformer extends
    AbstractExecutor
{
    /**
     * Params container
     */
    public static class Params
    {
        /**
         * Global data container (contains the
         *   top-level data).
         */
        public GlobalDataContainer _GDC = null;

        /**
         * Scenario data container factory (
         *   creates the object handling the
         *   scenario-level data).
         */
        public ScenarioDataContainerFactory
            _SDCF = null;

        /**
         * Trial data container factory (
         *   creates the object handling the
         *   trial-level data).
         */
        public TrialDataContainerFactory _TDCF
            = null;

        /**
         * If true, the notifications are
         *   expected to be printed to the
         *   console.
         */
        public boolean _notify = true;

        [...]
    }

    [...]

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param p params container
     */
}
```

```

45  */
public ExperimentPerformer(Params p)
{
    super(new Log(p._notify, p.
        _notifyGlobalLevel, p.
        _notifyCrossedScenariosLevel,
        p._notifyScenarioLevel, p.
        _notifyTrialLevel, p.
        _addTimestamp), 0);

    _GDC = p._GDC;
50  _SDCF = p._SDCF;
    _TDCF = p._TDCF;
}

/**
55  * The primary method that starts
    * executing the experiments.
    *
    * @return execution summary
    */
public Summary execute()
60 {
    return execute(null);
}

/**
65  * The primary method that starts
    * executing the experiments.
    *
    * @param args additional arguments that
    * can be passed via, e.g., the command
    * lines
    * @return execution summary
    */
70 public Summary execute(String[] args)
{
    Summary summary = instantiateSummary();
    // creates the main summary object
    summary.setStartTimestamp(LocalDateTime
        .now()); // set starting date
    doInitLog();

75  Parser parser = new Parser();
    Parser.Result r = null;
    if (args != null) r = parser.parse(args
        );

80  try
    {
        validateGDC();
        validateSDCF();
        validateTDCF();
85  instantiateGDC();
        createMainFolder();
        processScenarios(summary);
    } catch (
        AbstractExperimentationException e)
90 {
    terminate(summary, _log.
        printTerminationMessage(e));
    return summary;
}

```

```

    }

    finalize(summary);
    return summary;
}

[... ]
100 }

```

2.6.1. Running the experiments through the console [T]

Source package: `t1_t10.t5_experimentation_module`.
`t1_parser`

As Section 2.6 explains, the *ExperimentPerformer* can be passed various parameters through the console. This may be handy when, e.g., splitting the experimentation into different machines (e.g., machine #1 performs trials 0, ..., 49 and machine #2 trials 50, ..., 99). For this purpose, one has to produce a JAR file with appointed main class (*main* method), which should call “*execute(String [] args)*”. The console arguments (captured by *main*) should be passed to the executor’s method.

The passed arguments will be parsed via a simple *Parser* class (*parse* package). The initial release of JECDM allows for providing only a few yet meaningful commands that may suitably adjust the experimentation process. These are selecting the number of threads and defining the scenario/trial disabling conditions.

Each element of the passed *String [] args* is one argument. The arguments are first preprocessed: the white spaces are removed (nonetheless, they should be voided in the scope of one argument when provided via the console) and transformed into uppercase. Then, each such preprocessed element is analyzed. First, the command line arguments are assumed to come in the following format “*PARAMETER=VALUE*”. Currently, three parameters are available:

- **PARAMETER=THREADS:** This argument will adjust the number of threads. Its value should be a positive integer viewed as a string, e.g., “10”. Overall, the example argument can be “THREADS=10” (set the number of threads to 10).
- **PARAMETER=DISABLED_TRIALS:** This argument can introduce trial disabling conditions (exclude some trials from processing). The format is: “*DISABLED_TRIALS=[val1, val2,...]*”, where the *val* indicates ID of trials to be disabled (separated by commas). Further, the IDs can be expressed as intervals, e.g., “10-20”. Example argument: “*DISABLED_TRIALS=[10,20,50-99]*” (excludes trials 10, 20, and 50-99).
- **PARAMETER=DISABLED_SCENARIOS:** This argument can introduce scenario disabling conditions (exclude specific scenarios from processing). The format is: “*DISABLED_SCENARIOS=[sdc1, sdc2,...]*”, where *sdc*s are scenario disabling conditions (separated by commas). Each *sdc* corresponds to one *ScenarioDisablingCondition*

that will be added for processing (as it would be added via `GlobalDataContainer.Params`). Each `sdc` takes the following format: “(K1:V1;K2:V2;...)”, where `K:V` are selected keys and their values that constitute the disabling condition (as explained in Section 2.3.3; separated by semicolons).

This tutorial’s source code showcases parsing effects given various inputs. Note that the codes are synthetic, i.e., they exemplify how the `Parser` class operates within `ExperimentPerformer`. Overall, three small cases are introduced in the code. Note that the parsing results are provided in a report-like class used by `ExperimentPerformer` to adjust processing suitably. It provides methods for generating a log, and this functionality is used in this example. The three obtained logs are printed to the console, and the expected output is illustrated in Figure 3 for convenience.

Case #1. This short example exemplifies how to set the number of threads. The code is presented in Listing 19.

Listing 19: Tutorial’s case #1

```
String [] a = new String[]{"THREADS=100",};
Parser parser = new Parser();
Parser.Result result = parser.parse(a);
PrintUtils.printLines(result.generateLogLines());
```

Case #2. This case extends the previous one by introducing scenario disabling conditions. Note that the first argument contains lower-case letters. It does not matter because the input will be transformed into upper-case before interpreting the arguments.

Listing 20: Tutorial’s case #2

```
String [] a = new String[]
{
    "ThReADs=100",
    "DISABLED_TRIALS=[0-20,25,75-99]"
};
Parser parser = new Parser();
Parser.Result result = parser.parse(a);
PrintUtils.printLines(result.generateLogLines());
```

Case #3. This case introduces scenario disabling conditions (the keys and values should match the ones specified in `GlobalDataContainer`). Also, note that the user may specify the same argument-related params many times. However, only the last one will matter as it will overwrite the indicators of its predecessors (in this example, each of the same arguments is provided twice, but only the second ones matter).

Listing 21: Tutorial’s case #3

```
String [] a = new String[]
{
    "Threads=10",
    "ThReADs=50",
```

```
"DISABLED_TRIALS=[10]",
"DISABLED_TRIALS=[20]",
"SOMETHING_WRONG",
"ANOTHER_ERROR",
"DISABLED_SCENARIOS=[(KEY1:V11;KEY2:V23)
,(KEY1:V12)]",
"DISABLED_SCENARIOS=[(KEY4:V42; KEY3:V32)
,(KEY5:V51)]",
};
Parser parser = new Parser();
Parser.Result result = parser.parse(a);
PrintUtils.printLines(result.generateLogLines());
```

```
Case 1:
No. threads = 100
Scenario disabling conditions = not specified
Trial disabling conditions = not specified
Invalid arguments = none
Case 2:
No. threads = 100
Scenario disabling conditions = not specified
Trial disabling conditions = 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Invalid arguments = none
Case 3:
No. threads = 50
Scenario disabling conditions =
    KEY4_V42_KEY3_V32
    KEY5_V51
Trial disabling conditions = 20
Invalid arguments =
    SOMETHING_WRONG
    ANOTHER_ERROR
Process finished with exit code 0
```

Figure 3: Expected console output

3. Use case #1: The knapsack problem [T]

Source package: `t1_t10.t5_experimentation_module`.
`t2_knapsack_example` Source code: **Tutorial2a**

This tutorial showcases how to prepare a simple experiment using this module. The experiment concerns solving a knapsack problem using an evolutionary algorithm. The method will be tested given its different variants, problem complexity assumed, and computational resources given. Note that the tutorial is focused on just showing how to perform the experimentation. Therefore, the problems tackled will be easy to solve, and the algorithm will be straightforward.

Important note: The tutorial employs the algorithm presented in the document “*Tutorial 2: Evolutionary Computa-*

tion module – part 1: basics and single-objective optimization”. Therefore, the relevant codes will not be discussed here to avoid repetitions. The algorithm itself can be found in *knapsackea* package. There are a few changes, however, that must be discussed – they refer to the auxiliary *Data* class that provides the problem instance specification. First, the data is not pre-fixed this time. Instead, a simple data generator that creates a random instance given the number of items and bounds on their sizes and values is defined. Its implementation is the static *Data getInstance(int items, IRandom R, Range valuesBounds, IntRange sizesBounds)* method (of *Data* class) that – as the name suggests, returns a random problem instance (concrete instance of *Data* class). Second, the assumed capacity is not now a part of *Data* but is a concrete parameterization mean of the evolutionary algorithm (used by *KnapsackEvaluator*).

Overall, this tutorial will examine two variants of the already-introduced algorithm:

- variant employing a repairing procedure for dealing with knapsack overflow,
- variant penalizing infeasible solutions.

They will be tested given:

- The number of items (problem size): 50, 100, or 200 items.
- Knapsack capacity/size (problem-related parameter): 50, 100, or 200.
- The limit for the number of generations is 25, 50, or 100.
- Population size: 50, 100, or 200 specimens.

As for the performance metrics, the algorithms will be assessed given their best solution kept in each generation (attaining the best value). Note that, due to the implementation specifications of the algorithms, the best solution will always be stored – after sorting – at the index of 0 in the population.

The selected and relevant code snippets from **Tutorial2a** source code that exemplify how to design and perform the experiment are discussed in what follows. **Important note:** This tutorial produces only the lowest-level per-trial binary files in the ends. Their further processing will be discussed later in this document.

Let us start with Listing 22 first. The above-presented assumed experimental setting implies that only three *Data* objects are needed: for the number of items 50, 100, and 200. These objects contain just data on knapsack items and can be considered read-only. Thus, there is no reason to instantiate one such object for each algorithm. It would be a waste of resources. Instead, just these three required instances are created. They are stored in an associative array that will be later bounded with the global data container. This way, they will be free to access later. Listing 22 showcases a relatively straightforward piece of code. Note that the bound from which the item values are randomly drawn is set to [5, 10] (the bound is set to [2, 5] for item sizes). **Important note:** Depending on the particular experimentation case, pre-generating read-only problem data before

establishing the experiment may be considered good practice as it reduces the computational/memory burden. However, there is also an additional benefit. Assume that such *Data* objects are generated for each algorithm individually instead. If so, each method would have been given a different problem to solve (the coefficients are drawn randomly here), and the overall experiment would be methodologically incorrect.

Listing 22: Creating data for the knapsack problem

```
// Random number generator (common to all
// objects):
IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(0);
// No. items considered
int [] items = new int []{50, 100, 200};
// Map that will store data objects and
// will be shared across all scenarios
HashMap<Integer, Data> dataMap = new
    HashMap<>(items.length);
for (Integer it : items)
    dataMap.put(it, Data.getInstance(it, R,
        new Range(5.0d, 10.0d), new IntRange
            (2, 5)));
// Items (values) viewed as string (will be
// required when defining scenarios)
String [] sItems = new String[items.length
    ];
for (int i = 0; i < items.length; i++)
    sItems[i] = String.valueOf(items[i]);
```

Let’s move to Listing 23. It showcases how to create the params container of *GlobalDataContainer*. It also illustrates how to set three essential parameters: the path to the folder where the results will be stored (ensure that the path is valid in user’s system; adapt it to user’s needs, the number of trials (i.e., test runs), and the number of threads (the user may wish to lower the default number of 20 if their hardware contains a less powerful CPU).

Listing 23: GlobalDataContainer: basic parameters

```
// GLOBAL DATA CONTAINER =====
// Create the params container:
GlobalDataContainer.Params pGDC = new
    GlobalDataContainer.Params();
// Prepare random number generator
// constructor (it is recommended to leave
// it as it is - use the default
// constructor).
// pGDC._RNGI = new
    DefaultRandomNumberGeneratorInitializer
        ();
// Specify the main path for the folder
// where the results will be stored (
// IMPORTANT: adjust to your needs):
pGDC._mainPath = "E:\\knapsack_test";
// No. trials to be performed for each
// scenario (IDs = 0, 1,...,99)
pGDC._noTrials = 100;
```

```

// Split processing into threads (Important
// note: use value that is similar to your
// no. physical cores,
// and gives no. trials % no. threads == 0)
pGDC._noThreads = 20;

```

Listing 24 moves to establishing scenario definitions (keys and values). Note that the values (array) are mapped 1:1 to keys via index (i.e., “Penalty” and “Repair” are assumed associated with the key “Algorithm”). Additionally, as already explained, the keys/values will be standardized (thus, they will be converted into upper cases).

Listing 24: GlobalDataContainer: defining scenarios

```

// Defined scenario keys (labels/
// definitions); note that the key/values
// will be standardized (check the JavaDoc)
// here, they will be transformed into
// upper cases:
pGDC._scenarioKeys = new String[]{
    "Algorithm", // 0
    "Items", // 1
    "Capacity", // 2
    "Generations", // 3
    "pS"}; // 4 (population size)

// Define scenario values (1:1 mapping with
// keys):
pGDC._scenarioValues = new String[][]{
    {"Penalty", "Repair"}, // 0
    sItems, // 1
    {"50", "100", "200"}, // 2
    {"25", "50", "100"}, // 3
    {"50", "100", "200"} // 4
};

```

Next, Listing 25 shows how to supply the container with the *Data* objects constructed at the beginning. It also parameterizes the auxiliary monitor thread (reports the trial threads execution process) and creates the global data container.

Listing 25: GlobalDataContainer: further basic parameters

```

// Associative arrays that can be used to
// store some custom data can be stored in
// the following way
// (the maps for a given level are
// accessible from the same level and all
// levels below; thus, the map below
// will be accessible at the global,
// scenario, and trial level). Let's store
// the pre-instantiated
// data objects (are considered read only
// -- but they are not immutable), so that
// they will be already accessible:
pGDC._mapObject = new HashMap<>();
pGDC._mapObject.put("DATA", dataMap); //
// there is also map for double, integer,
// and string

```

```

// Monitor thread = reports the progress on
// executing a scenario. The report will
// be printed into the console
// after each provided ms (reporting
// interval).
pGDC._useMonitorThread = true; // turn on (
// true by default)
pGDC._monitorReportingInterval = 1000; //
// set to 1000 ms

// Create object instance (we will not use
// it in this example; the container is
// utilized by the ExperimentPerformer
// class):
GlobalDataContainer GDC = new
GlobalDataContainer(pGDC);

```

Listing 26 moves to creating the scenario data container factory (params container). It focuses on conditionally setting the number of generations (setting the respective initializer). There are two ways to achieve this. The first way can be called straightforward. The value for the key “GENERATIONS” of a scenario being processed can be derived from *p.scenario.getKeyValuesMap()* and inspected (as shown in the code). However, as already explained, the “GENERATIONS” key is “special”, meaning some shortcuts are available. The last line – commented out – shows how the second way (shortcut) of deriving the generations limit given the scenario characteristics.

Listing 26: ScenarioDataContainerFactory: specifying the number of generations

```

// SCENARIO DATA CONTAINER FACTORY =====
ScenarioDataContainerFactory.Params pSDCF =
    new ScenarioDataContainerFactory.Params
    ();

[...]

// Using the below line will force all
// scenarios to consider the limit for the
// number of generations = 100.
// pSDCF._generations = 100;
// However, the module lets you change the
// parameters conditionally if the (
// condition = scenario's key/values).
// For this purpose, you can implement a
// dedicated interface consisting of one
// method (lambda method can
// be used; if there is no desired
// dedicated method, you can extend the
// default factory class to customize it).
// For instance, the below line will set
// the number of generations as provided
// via the scenario's key value.
// Note that the input is the scenario's
// params container filled by the executor
// and passed to the factory in
// order to create the scenario data
// container instance (dedicated to a
// specific scenario setting):
pSDCF._numberOfGenerationsInitializer = p

```

```

-> {
15 // p = scenario's params container filled
    // by the experiment executor
    // _scenario: scenario object (provides
    // data on the scenario being processed;
    // particularly on key-values)
    // keyValuesMap = allows retrieving
    // current scenario value for a specified
    // key (note that using keyValues
    // is faster, but may be prone to errors
    // due to the fact that GDC may alter the
    // orders in which keys are stored).
    // getValue() = Value object; next
    // getValue gives its string
    // representation
20 return Integer.parseInt(p._scenario.
    getKeyValuesMap().get("GENERATIONS").
    getValue());
    // Shortcut can also be used for "
    GENERATIONS":
    //return p._scenario.getGenerations();
};

```

Next, the employed algorithms are generational, which means that their steady-state repeats should be set to a default value of 1 (unconditionally, see Listing 27; note that the default field value is either way 1, so this line could be skipped).

Listing 27: ScenarioDataContainerFactory: setting the number of steady state repeats

```

// Similar pattern exists for the expected
// number of steady state repeats:
pSDCF._steadyStateRepeats = 1; // will
// assume a constant value (= default value
// )
// pSDCF.
// _numberOfSteadyStateRepeatsInitializer =
// null; // you can implement this
// initializer to customize the indications

```

Listing 28 presents how to define the performance indicators. As outlined at the beginning, the methods will be assessed given their best solutions kept in each generation, which are stored as first specimens in their population arrays (due to implementation specification). Note that *FirstSpecimenEvaluation* indicator is used – in fact, two instances. This indicator assesses the algorithm given the performance of the first specimen in the population (implicitly assumed to be the best). Note that the implementations define performance as a two-element vector: [knapsack value; knapsack size]. The integers passed to the constructors and indices point to the elements of the performance vector. Thus, the first indicator returns knapsack size, while the second knapsack value. The second argument is the indicator's preference direction (*false* for the first indicator means that higher values are preferred, while *true* for the latter favors lesser sizes). These directions are essential for some summarizers (e.g., *CrossSummarizer*) can use them when determining rankings of algorithms).

Listing 28: ScenarioDataContainerFactory: defining the performance indicators

```

// Let's use two indicators (
// unconditionally). Indicator should
// return a performance value for an
// algorithm
// in specific iteration (and trial run).
// The first indicator will return the 0-th
// performance value
// associated with the first population
// member (assumed to be the best one; 0-th
// element = value). The second
// indicator concerns 1-th element (size).
pSDCF._indicators = new IIndicator[2];
pSDCF._indicators[0] = new
    FirstSpecimenEvaluation(0, false); // 0-
// th element; less is preferred = false
pSDCF._indicators[1] = new
    FirstSpecimenEvaluation(1, true); // 1-
// th element; less is preferred = true
// pSDCF._indicatorsInitializer = null;
// performance indicators can also be
// defined conditionally

```

Next, Listing 29 finalizes the construction of the scenario data container factory. Note that the code additionally sets the data storing interval. However, it is set to a limit far exceeding the generation limits assumed, thus has no effect. However, it was put here to remind users that they may try adjusting it to improve overall memory usage.

Listing 29: ScenarioDataContainerFactory: further basic parameters

```

// The field below can be adjusted to
// balance memory consumption and hard
// drive input operations (default value
// = Integer.MAX_VALUE). Generally, the EA's
// assessment (per trial) is stored in a
// matrix (rows = generations X
// columns = indicators). For the default
// setting, the assessment is completed
// when the algorithm finishes
// processing and only after the data is
// moved from the memory into binary files.
// However, the field below
// steers the maximum number of rows in the
// results matrix. During the algorithm
// execution, if the allowed
// capacity is overflowed, the data is
// flushed to the files, and the matrix is
// cleared. Overall, the smaller
// the interval, the lesser the memory
// consumption, but the disc input
// operations are more frequently executed.
pSDCF._dataStoringInterval = 1000; // more
// than for any scenario (so does not
// affect)
// Create the factory:
ScenarioDataContainerFactory SDCF = new
    ScenarioDataContainerFactory(pSDCF);

```

Listing 30 moves to creating a trial data container factory. As explained in Section 2.5, this will often boil down to defining an

evolutionary algorithm conditionally on the scenario being processed – and this is the case of this tutorial example. For this purpose, the code creates the initializer of an evolutionary algorithm. It inspects the (i) number of knapsack items assumed in the currently processed scenario, (ii) the knapsack capacity, (iii) populations size, and (iv) algorithm. Additionally, it retrieves the *Data* object stored in the global data container’s associative array. Finally, the code uses all these components to create a concrete instance of *EA* that the initializer returns.

Listing 30: TrialDataContainerFactory: defining the evolutionary algorithm

```

// TRIAL DATA CONTAINER FACTORY =====
TrialDataContainerFactory.Params pTDCF =
    new TrialDataContainerFactory.Params();

[...]

// Creating EA should be conditional:
pTDCF._eaInitializer = (R1, p) -> {
    // Retrieve parameterization:
    // You need to use p._SDC.getScenario()
    // -- access via scenario data container
    // upper case due to standardization
    int it = Integer.parseInt(p._SDC.
        getScenario().getKeyValuesMap().get("
            ITEMS").getValue());
    int capacity = Integer.parseInt(p._SDC.
        getScenario().getKeyValuesMap().get("
            CAPACITY").getValue());
    int populationSize = Integer.parseInt(p.
        _SDC.getScenario().getKeyValuesMap().
        get("PS").getValue());
    boolean repair = p._SDC.getScenario().
        getKeyValuesMap().get("ALGORITHM").
        getValue().equals("REPAIR");

    // Data map is accessible from here, so
    // the below line would work:
    // Data data = dataMap.get(10);
    // This line shows how to retrieve the
    // map from GDC:
    @SuppressWarnings("unchecked") //
        unchecked cast due to type erasure
    HashMap<Integer, Data> dm = (HashMap<
        Integer, Data>) p._SDC.getGDC().
        getObject("DATA");
    Data data = dm.get(it);

    [...]

    return Utils.getKnapsackEA(populationSize
        , data, capacity, repair, R1);
};

// Default runner initializer is
// recommended. It:
// - Disables visualization
// - Uses the number of steady-state
// repeats as imposed the scenario data
// container
// The default initializer is already set,

```

```

    so the line below has no effect:
    /// pTDCF._runnerInitializer = new
    DefaultRunnerInitializer();

    // Create the factory:
    TrialDataContainerFactory TDCF = new
    TrialDataContainerFactory(pTDCF);

```

One may execute the **Tutorial2a** source code to perform the experiment. The expected per-scenario results (per-trial binary files) will be created in dedicated folders in the main folder specified (by default, in “*E:\knapsack_test*”). Note that the experiment is moderately complex, and the algorithms employed are relatively fast. Thus, the experiment should not take much time to finalize, but it is hardware-dependent, of course. For example, it took around 22 seconds for the AMD Threadripper 1950X with 16 cores (when run with a thread pool size of 20). It is up to the reader to investigate thoroughly the code, the process, and the results. For convenience, Figure 4 and 5 bring the beginning of the expected console output (focused on the first processed scenario) and the ending (the summary). Note that this experiment, in total, involves 2 (algorithm variants) · 3 (problem sizes) · 3 (knapsack capacities) · 3 (generations limit) · 3 (population sizes) = 162 scenarios, as reflected in the final summary (the number of successfully completed scenarios). Additionally, Figure 6 showcases example per-scenario folders created by *ExperimentPerformer*, while Figure 7 a few of the binary files created for one selected scenario. Observe that the names combine the indicator’s name (“FSE0” or “FSE1” – FSE stands for *FirstSpecimenEvaluation*) with trial ID. Finally, it is worth reporting that the executor produced in total 32400 per-trial result files (no. scenarios = 162 · 2 (no. indicators) · 100 (no. trials) = 32400). These files consume around 14.4 MB (42.1 MB of disc space), which is not much given the complexity of the experimental setting.

4. Understanding fundamental concepts (continuation)

The per-trial results generated by *ExperimentPerformer* provide rich data on the employed algorithms’ performance in various contexts. Nonetheless, these raw, unprocessed files require further processing before conclusions can be drawn. For this reason, two additional executors are supplied with the initial release of JECMD:

- *ScenariosSummarizer*: Aggregates the per-trial result into per-scenario summary-like files. The aggregation is done by employing statistical functions that produce one representative assessment from a series of them attained by a method in all trials.
- *CrossSummarizer*: Performs complex cross-comparisons of obtained results. The constructed result files help observe changes in performance when comparing different scenarios that are products of crossing the values of their pre-selected keys (sensitivity analysis).

Important note: Both executors are built on *ExperimentPerformer*: (i) they employ the same data containers (factories) –

```

[3.12.2024 15:6:58:745]: Experiment execution starts
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:754]: Instantiates the global data container
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:762]: The main folder is created (E:\knapsack_test)
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:762]: Beginning processing the scenarios
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:772]: Experimental scenario = GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_50_ALGORITHM_PENALTY begins processing
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:772]: Creates a scenario-related folder
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:772]: Creates the count down latch (barrier)
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:772]: Creates trial executors
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:794]: Creates a trial (thread) pool
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:796]: Attempting to instantiate the monitor thread
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:796]: Instantiate the monitor thread with reporting interval = 1000
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:798]: Attempting to instantiate the monitor thread executor
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:798]: Executes the monitor thread
[3.12.2024 15:6:58:799]: Executes the threads
[3.12.2024 15:6:59:341]: ALL threads terminated/completed processing
[3.12.2024 15:6:59:341]: Experimental scenario = GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_50_ALGORITHM_PENALTY ends processing
[3.12.2024 15:6:59:341]: Scenario = GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_50_ALGORITHM_PENALTY processing time = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 0, millis = 578]
[3.12.2024 15:6:59:341]: Total number of trials = 100
[3.12.2024 15:6:59:341]: Successfully completed trials = 100
[3.12.2024 15:6:59:341]: Terminated trials (due to exception) = 0
[3.12.2024 15:6:59:341]: Disposes the thread pool
[3.12.2024 15:6:59:341]: Disposes the scenario data container

```

Figure 4: Beginning of the log produced by ExperimentPerformer

```

THE SUMMARY OF THE EXECUTION PROCESS
Started = [3.12.2024 15:6:58:742]
Ended = [3.12.2024 15:7:18:952]
Took = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 20, millis = 210]
Termination due to exception = false
Total number of scenarios = 162
Successfully completed scenarios = 162 (may include cases where not all trials were completed)
Terminated scenarios (due to exception) = 0
Skipped scenarios (due to being disabled) = 0
Successfully completed trials (in total) = 16200
Terminated trials (due to exception; in total) = 0
Skipped trials (due to being disabled; in total) = 0

```

Figure 5: Ending of the log produced by ExperimentPerformer

GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_50_ALGORITHM_PENALTY	03.12.2024 15:06
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_50_ALGORITHM_REPAIR	03.12.2024 15:06
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_100_ALGORITHM_PENALTY	03.12.2024 15:06
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_100_ALGORITHM_REPAIR	03.12.2024 15:06
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_200_ALGORITHM_PENALTY	03.12.2024 15:06
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_200_ALGORITHM_REPAIR	03.12.2024 15:06
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_PS_50_ALGORITHM_PENALTY	03.12.2024 15:07
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_PS_50_ALGORITHM_REPAIR	03.12.2024 15:07
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_PS_100_ALGORITHM_PENALTY	03.12.2024 15:07
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_PS_100_ALGORITHM_REPAIR	03.12.2024 15:07
GENERATIONS_25_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_PS_200_ALGORITHM_PENALTY	03.12.2024 15:07

Figure 6: Example per-scenario folders

FSE0_0.bin	03.12.2024 15:06
FSE0_1.bin	03.12.2024 15:06
FSE0_2.bin	03.12.2024 15:06
FSE0_3.bin	03.12.2024 15:06
FSE0_4.bin	03.12.2024 15:06
FSE0_5.bin	03.12.2024 15:06
FSE0_6.bin	03.12.2024 15:06
FSE0_7.bin	03.12.2024 15:06
FSE0_8.bin	03.12.2024 15:06

Figure 7: Example binary files

the same object instances can be used, and (ii) rely on the binary files created by *ExperimentPerformer*. If either (i) or (ii) is not satisfied, the execution process will fail. The following sections will discuss both classes. In short, one has to define the data containers (factories) and run *ExperimentPerformer* first. Then, the remaining executors can be applied using the same data.

4.1. *ScenariosSummarizer* class [T]

Source package: *t1_t10.t5_experimentation_module*.
t2_knapsack_example Source code: **Tutorial2b**

ScenariosSummarizer employs so-called “*scenario savers*” (see *IScenarioSaver* interface in *io.scenario* package) to construct per-scenario summary results files. These files aggregate the per-trial results obtained by an algorithm using pre-selected

Figure 8: Example result generated by SummarizerXLSX (generations = 50; items = 200; capacity = 50; population size = 100; algorithm = *repair*)

statistic functions (see the *IStatistic* interface in the *statistics* package in the *Utils* module). In short, assume that the algorithm’s assessments for each trial – given some specific generation and a performance indicator – are available as a vector. The intention is to apply selected statistic functions to each such vector to summarize the individual test runs.

The initial release of JECMD provides four default scenario summarizers (available in *io.scenario* package):

- **SummarizerXLSX:** This summarizer produces an Excel XLSX file. It creates a dedicated tab for each performance indicator used. Within one tab, the per-trial results are summarized in a table, where columns are linked to statistic functions, while rows with generations. This file format supports cell styles and includes simple convergence plots that visualize how the statistics on the performance assessment given specific indicators changed throughout all generations. The example file created by this saver is depicted in Figure 8 for convenience (the file is linked to the “Knapsack” case study).
- **SummarizerXLS:** As with *SummarizerXLSX*, but does not use cell styles and generate convergence plots.
- **SummarizerCSV:** Similarly to the two above, but the tables (tabs) are stored in a single CSV file. Specifically, each per-indicator result block starts with three lines containing the indicator’s name, statistics’ names (column headers), and the number indicating the following number of relevant rows (generations); see the example output presented in Figure 8 (CSV counterpart of the result presented in Figure 9). The blocks are stored one by one.
- **SummarizerTXT:** As *SummarizerCSV*, but viewed as a TXT file.

Important note: The scenario savers create the files in respective per-scenario folders (so the files summarizing a sce-

FSE0	MIN	MEAN	MAX	STD
50				
198.26946	203.48872	208.84974	2.330823746	199728
198.26946	203.48872	208.84974	2.330823746	199747
198.74937	205.28598	211.74848	2.243851301	220938
201.54031	207.41225	213.94503	2.417042017	709878
203.51596	209.75581	215.50583	2.184350490	741306
206.29949	211.65975	215.84724	1.818538079	593646
208.20043	212.91329	215.84724	1.585578444	3976901
209.15666	213.85871	215.84724	1.315079225	90775
211.92835	214.51566	215.84724	1.009886521	3629964
212.06796	215.10249	215.84724	0.807596219	8805321
212.91682	215.45966	215.84724	0.590476972	2591562
213.95521	215.66331	215.84724	0.357617297	4397805
214.29152	215.74333	215.84724	0.276517672	8964176
214.63293	215.80612	215.84724	0.149202647	0493996
214.76379	215.82039	215.84724	0.119169591	82668041
214.76379	215.82737	215.84724	0.114268166	70216874
214.76379	215.83365	215.84724	0.109354281	06989535
215.01398	215.83891	215.84724	0.083325710	60581627
215.06457	215.83941	215.84724	0.078266940	009353877
215.15634	215.84033	215.84724	0.069089969	04241727
215.15634	215.84033	215.84724	0.069089969	04241736
215.67559	215.84552	215.84724	0.017165183	053293665
215.67559	215.84552	215.84724	0.017165183	053293693
215.76736	215.84644	215.84724	0.007988212	200217507

Figure 9: Example result generated by SummarizerCSV (generations = 50; items = 200; capacity = 50; population size = 100; algorithm = *repair*)

nario are stored in the same folders as where the input per-trial results are stored).

This tutorial’s source code (**Tutorial2b**) is a straightforward adaptation of **Tutorial2a** – most of the code is copied and pasted, and the comments indicate what was added. It is not

too much as using **ScenarioSummarizer** requires two things (apart from creating the object instance and calling its *execute()* method):

- The scenario savers have to be specified at the global level. Listing 31 brings relevant code snippet that showcases how it can be accomplished (*SummarizerXLSX* and *SummarizerCSV* are used).
- The statistic functions that will be used to aggregate outcomes of different trials must be defined – this is showcased in Listing 32 (*Min*, *Mean*, *Max*, and *StandardDeviation* are used). Note that the order in which these functions are specified matters, as it will be reflected in the resulting files.

Additionally, the source code introduces the “*dataLoadingInterval*” parameter. It plays a similar role to “*dataStoringIntervall*” but represents the limit for data matrices used by scenario savers when loading results stored in binary files.

Overall, the *ScenarioSummarizer* used in *Tutorial2b* will summarize the results, at the scenario level, produced by **Tutorial2a**. Two extra files (XLSX and CSV) are expected to be produced per scenario and contained in respective folders. It is up to the reader to get acquainted with the results in detail. Note that the summarizer will produce a final console output similar to the one presented in Figure 6.

Listing 31: ScenarioSummarizer: defining the statistic functons

```
// The ‘savers’ are responsible for
// creating per-scenario result files. The
// object used below will provide the
// aggregated results (obtained through
// statistic functions) in an Excel file,
// where the columns will represent
// different statistics, while rows will be
// associated with generations. Further,
// results obtained according
// to different indicators will be
// presented in different tabs.
pGDC._referenceScenarioSavers = new
LinkedList<>();
pGDC._referenceScenarioSavers.add(new
SummarizerXLSX());
pGDC._referenceScenarioSavers.add(new
SummarizerCSV(’,’));
```

Listing 32: ScenarioSummarizer: defining the statistic functons

```
// Statistic functions used to summarize
// trial outcomes:
pSDCF._statistics = new IStatistic[4];
pSDCF._statistics[0] = new Min();
pSDCF._statistics[1] = new Mean();
pSDCF._statistics[2] = new Max();
pSDCF._statistics[3] = new
StandardDeviation();
pSDCF._statisticFunctionsInitializer = null
;
```

4.2. CrossSummarizer class [T]

Source package: *t1_t10.t15_experimentation_module.t2_knapsack_example* Source code: **Tutorial2c**

CrossSummarizer is a powerful executor for performing cross-analysis/comparison/etc. The idea is to consider a subset of provided keys and inspect the attained results given different their values. For instance, consider the following artificial scenario. There are three keys and their values: ALGORITHM = [NSGA, NSGAI], PROBLEM = [DTLZ1, DTLZ2, DTLZ3, ..., DTLZ7], and OBJECTIVES=[2,3,4,5] (the number of objectives for the multi-objective problem). Imagine that one wishes to investigate the algorithm’s performance given each problem. At the same time, the user is not particularly interested in cross-examining these results against the number of objectives. Thus, in some sense, the results can be represented as tables, one per each number of objectives considered, and the table’s rows and columns are linked to algorithms and problems. We will be calling the selection of the two former keys (ALGORITHM; PROBLEM) a crossed setting, and the overall Cartesian product of crossing over their values: crossed scenarios.

JECDM introduces a dedicated class that allows defining custom crossed scenarios: *CrossedSetting* (see *scenario* package). Listing 33 showcases how it can be employed to define the above scenario. **Important notes:**

- At least one crossed setting must be provided via params container to *CrossedSummarizer*.
- When defining the crossed setting, a subset of keys from the main key set must be specified. Here, the subset is ALGORITHM and PROBLEM, while the main set is ALGORITHM, PROBLEM, and OBJECTIVES.
- The input string will be standardized (will be converted into upper cases).
- The order in which the keys are provided matters as it will be reflected by the order in which the so-called cross-savers examine the results.
- The number of selected keys may be different than two. In general, it can be any positive number (it will be explained later). **Important definition:** The number of keys is considered a level (or dimensionality) of crossed setting.
- For each key, its subset of original values must be specified (one does not need to specify all of them). E.g., if the values for PROBLEM are DTLZ1, DTLZ2, ..., DTLZ7, one can select, e.g., DTLZ1 and DTLZ2 (as done in the example code snippet). It means the results will be cross-examined given some strict selection of keys and values. In Listing 33, ALGORITHM is associated with NSGA and NSGA-II, while PROBLEM is with DTLZ1 and DTLZ2 (1:1 association via index).
- As with the keys, the order in which the values are provided matters.

Listing 33: CrossedSetting class

```

pGDC._crossedSettings = new CrossedSetting
    [1];
// keys/values will be standardized
pGDC._crossedSettings[0] = new
    CrossedSetting(new String[]{"algorithm",
        "PROBLEM"}, new String[][]{{"NSGA", "
        NSGAI1"}, {"DTLZ1", "DTLZ2"}});

```

When running *CrossExaminer*, the scenarios will be associated with specified so-called cross-savers (*ICrossSaver* interface in *io.cross* package). Note that the concrete implementations of *ICrossSaver* may restrict the dimensionality of crossed settings with which they can be coupled (e.g., a cross-saver may be designed to work only with 2-level settings, where two keys are selected for cross-examination). A crossed setting will be processed only if at least one matching saver is appointed. The matching will be done via *CrossExaminer* automatically.

A crossed setting explicitly defines which keys will be compared one against another in a single result file. In turn, it is assumed that the keys that are not selected will be fixed (their values). Of course, multiple keys may be assigned to a key. Thus, there may be multiple ways of fixing them. Consequently, a Cartesian product will be constructed from non-selected keys' values when processing a crossed setting. It will represent all possible ways of fixing the non-selected keys. In this view, the produced cross-results will be determined conditionally on the concrete fixing. For instance, consider the example keys and their values introduced above and the crossed setting in Listing 33. Here, only one key is not selected: OBJECTIVES, whose values will be used for fixing (2, 3, 4, 5). **Important note:** The cross-examination results produced by *CrossExaminer* will be stored in a dedicated folder. It is named "CROSSED_RESULTS" by default, but it may be changed via the global data container (params container). Further, when a crossed setting is to be processed, the resulting results will be stored in dedicated folders whose names take the following form: FIXED_KEY_{f1}_VALUE_{f1}-..._KEY_{fm}_VALUE_{fm}-COMPARED_KEY_{c1}-..._KEY_{cn}, where *m* denotes the number of keys selected as fixed (and their values; *fi* denotes *i*-th fixed key/value), while *n* reflects the number of crossed keys (*cj* – denotes *j*-th crossed key). For instance, in the above example, the creation of 4 sub-folders can be expected, where each is related to a different crossed scenario resulting from the crossed setting:

- FIXED.OBJECTIVES.2.COMPARED.ALGORITHM.PROBLEM
- FIXED.OBJECTIVES.3.COMPARED.ALGORITHM.PROBLEM
- FIXED.OBJECTIVES.4.COMPARED.ALGORITHM.PROBLEM
- FIXED.OBJECTIVES.4.COMPARED.ALGORITHM.PROBLEM

Overall, the folder names are composed of two segments: (i) the first segment indicating which keys are not selected for cross-comparison and how they were set, (ii) and the second, which keys are crossed (compared). Note that the values for the latter are not provided as they are supposed to be an inherent part of the result files. Note that "NONE" will follow "FIXED" when all keys are selected for comparison.

The initial release of JECMD introduces a few valuable cross-savers that can be employed by *CrossSummarizer* to produce highly refined results. However, let us first move to the source code to introduce these savers (**Tutorial2c** source code). As with the preceding tutorial, this one can be deemed a direct continuation of **Tutorial2a** (most of the code is copied and pasted for simplicity).

Listing 34 brings a code snippet showcasing assumed crossed settings. Note that they were defined arbitrarily to a large extent, and the reader is advised to experiment with the code on their own. Observe that a single 1-level crossed setting is defined but commented out. The reason was to avoid creating an excessive number of crossed scenarios (there are 5 keys in this scenario in total; thus, crossed scenarios would result from a Cartesian product of values of 4 keys). Overall, one 2-level setting (keys = GENERATIONS, ALGORITHM; in that order) and one 3-level (keys = GENERATIONS, PS, ALGORITHM) are defined.

Listing 34: Creating crossed settings

```

// Default folder for crossed results:
//pGDC._crossedFolderName = "
    CROSSED_RESULTS";

pGDC._crossedSettings = new CrossedSetting
    [2];
// keys/values will be standardized
//pGDC._crossedSettings[0] = new
    CrossedSetting(
//
    new String[]{"algorithm"},
//
    new String[][]{{"PENALTY", "
    REPAIR"}}); // level = 1, NOTE: level 1
    is avoided, it produces
//
    large number of result files
pGDC._crossedSettings[0] = new
    CrossedSetting(new String[]{"
    GENERATIONS", "algorithm"}, new String
    [][]{{"25", "50", "100"}, {"PENALTY", "
    REPAIR"}}); // level = 2
pGDC._crossedSettings[1] = new
    CrossedSetting(new String[]{"GENERATIONS
    ", "PS", "algorithm"}, new String[][]{{"
    25", "50", "100"}, {"50", "100", "200"},
    {"PENALTY", "REPAIR"}}); // level = 3

```

As already explained, *CrossSummarizer* will match the crossed settings with some pre-selected cross-savers based on the level (each crossed scenario will be processed by each of its assigned savers). The savers must be provided the level with which they operate upon creation. Listing 35 brings the code snippet showcasing how and what savers are used in this tutorial. The integers passed via the constructor are the associated levels (thus if one wishes to couple a saver with two different levels, two suitably parameterized instances must be created). Overall, three different classes can be observed: *ConvergenceXLSX*, *FinalStatisticsXLSX*, and *FinalRankerXLSX*. Each of these savers will represent the result of crossed-examination in an Excel file (XLSX). Note that the XLS counterparts of these classes are also available. These savers are discussed, one

by one, in the following. **Important note:** Most of these savers operate using the *IStatistic* functions used to aggregate outcomes of different trials. These are the same statistic functions that are used by *ScenariosSummarizer* (thus, they are to be provided in the same way, i.e., via “*_statistics*” field of the params container for *ScenarioDataContainerFactory*). This tutorial’s source code employs min, mean, max, and standard deviation. Finally, note that *CrossSummarizer* also provides reports to the console when executed. Figure 10 illustrates the expected ending report (summary) – 36 different crossed settings have been processed. Example resulting folders are illustrated Figure 11. They are stored in the produced **CROSSED_RESULTS** folder.

Listing 35: Creating cross-savers

```

pGDC._referenceCrossSavers = new LinkedList
    <>();
// Convergence:
pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    ConvergenceXLSX(1));
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    ConvergenceXLS(1));
5 pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    ConvergenceXLSX(2));
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    ConvergenceXLS(2));
pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    ConvergenceXLSX(3));
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    ConvergenceXLS(3));

10 // Final statistics:
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalStatisticsXLSX(1)); // does not
    work for lv = 1
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalStatisticsXLS(1)); // does not work
    for lv = 1
pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalStatisticsXLSX(2));
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalStatisticsXLS(2));
15 pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalStatisticsXLSX(3));
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalStatisticsXLS(3));

// Final ranker:
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalRankerXLSX("ALGORITHM", 1)); //
    does not work for lv = 1
20 //pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalRankerXLS("ALGORITHM", 1)); // does
    not work for lv = 1
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalRankerXLSX("ALGORITHM", 2));
// Includes T-test (two-sided):
pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalRankerXLSX("ALGORITHM",
    new ITest[] {TStudent.getPairedTest(true)},
    2));
25 //pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new

```

```

    FinalRankerXLS("ALGORITHM",
    //new ITest[] {TStudent.getPairedTest(true)
    }, 2));
pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalRankerXLSX("ALGORITHM", 3));
//pGDC._referenceCrossSavers.add(new
    FinalRankerXLS("ALGORITHM", 3));

```

```

[3.12.2024 15:13:18:291]: Savers: notifying processing ends
[3.12.2024 15:13:18:386]: Savers: closing files
[3.12.2024 15:13:18:561]: Executing the finalization method
[3.12.2024 15:13:18:561]: Disposing the GDC data
[3.12.2024 15:13:18:561]: Experiment execution stops
THE SUMMARY OF THE CROSS-EXAMINATION PROCESS
Started = [3.12.2024 15:13:2:783]
Ended = [3.12.2024 15:13:18:561]
Took = [days = 0, hours = 0, minutes = 0, seconds = 15, millis = 778]
Termination due to exception = false
Total number of crossed scenarios = 36
Successfully completed crossed scenarios = 36
Terminated (due to exception) crossed scenarios = 0

```

Figure 10: Ending of the log produced by CrossSummarizer

```

FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_PS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_50_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_100_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_50_PS_200_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_PS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_PS_50_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_PS_100_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_100_PS_200_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_200_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_PS_ALGORITHM
FIXED_ITEMS_50_CAPACITY_200_PS_50_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_ALGORITHM

```

Figure 11: Example folders created by CrossSummarizer

ConvergenceXLSX (or *XLS*). As the name suggests, this saver produces Excel result files illustrating the progression of the employed algorithms given the assumed performance indicators. Overall, it helps create convergence plots. Consider Figure 12. It illustrates the Excel file generated in this tutorial for the scenario “FIXED_ITEMS_100_CAPACITY_100_PS_100_COMPARED_GENERATIONS_ALGORITHM”. This result follows a general structure imposed by the saver. Its properties are as follows:

- The resulting file will be named: “the name of the folder (provides data on fixed and compared keys) + *_convergenceMD.xlsx*”, where *M* denotes the level of the crossed scenario.
- Results concerning different indicators are stored in different tabs.
- The first column is reserved for the generation number.

Figure 12: Example result generated by ConvergenceXLSX (fixed items = 100; fixed capacity = 100; compared keys = GENERATIONS, PS, ALGORITHM)

GENERATIONS	PS	ALGORITHM	PENALTY				REPAIR			
			MIN	MEAN	MAX	STD	MIN	MEAN	MAX	STD
			50	100	200	50	100	200		
1	FSE0		238,075032	261,6848845	280,3270313	8,367954004	307,8473805	313,8418089	316,1609649	1,554996625
2	25	PS	251,085166	270,4224457	285,6035435	6,890628042	311,2608543	315,1344413	316,1609649	0,874822756
3			263,5108667	278,8187732	292,3096361	5,766036977	314,6608527	315,9371459	316,1609649	0,432814162
4	50	PS	264,1141609	283,0694945	298,9570496	7,386440423	308,7649591	314,6525108	316,1609649	1,35660931
5			274,1087029	293,8795995	305,6258445	6,232745697	312,7397772	315,4752246	316,1609649	0,787808777
6	100	PS	291,5092537	302,093938	310,9437558	3,836319531	314,2558749	315,9751678	316,1609649	0,456094134
7			285,7387448	299,867305	310,8220955	4,881587416	311,4101422	314,8354455	316,1609649	1,022495666
8	50	PS	298,2445912	307,4700916	314,0584931	3,065601712	314,3803482	315,7347345	316,1609649	0,595292579
9			307,2859613	311,9245615	315,0896578	1,797774813	314,5171924	315,9849391	316,1609649	0,409792923

Figure 13: Example result generated by FinalStatisticsXLSX (fixed items = 100; fixed capacity = 100; compared keys = GENERATIONS, PS, ALGORITHM)

- Remaining columns have a header that consists of two parts. The top segment represents all possible realizations (ways of fixing value) for crossed keys (the keys here are GENERATIONS, PS, and ALGORITHM – in that order). The segment below (one row) is linked to all statistics employed to aggregate test run outcomes (MIN, MEAN, MAX, and STD in this example).
- The main part of the table provides statistics attained by the employed algorithm given a specific scenario and statistics. **Important note:** many columns in Figure 12 are hidden for better visibility (only scenarios with GENERATIONS = 25 are presented).
- Finally, some auxiliary convergence plots that concern each scenario are provided on the right (each plot provides statistics attained by the method across generations when tackling a specific scenario).

file name will consist of the crossed scenario string representation ended with “_finalStatisticsMD.xlsx”, where *M* denotes the level. Additionally, note that *ConvergenceXLSX* can be coupled with crossed settings with a dimensionality of at least 2.

Figure 13 illustrates the example result for the same scenario as when discussing *ConvergenceXLSX*. Note that the last key specified is used as the primary table header. The remaining ones are employed on the left, and all their possible realizations are listed. The values stored in the main body are the results attained by the algorithm in the last generation given all scenarios, summarized by the statistic function employed. **Example interpretation of the results:** These results indicate that method incorporating the repairing procedure performs much better and is more stable than its “PENALTY” counterpart (better means – FSE0 is to be maximized, lower standard deviations = better stability). Additionally, they show that the increase in the number of generations/population size positively affects the results (which is usually apparent).

Note that – as already explained – the order of keys and values specified when defining the crossed setting will affect the order in which they appear in presented files. Additionally, mark that *ConvergenceXLSX* can be coupled with any crossed setting whose level is at least 1. The dimensionality of crossed scenarios will affect only the size (width) of the main header, as it is supposed to represent all ways of fixing their values.

FinalRankerXLSX (or XLS). While *ConvergenceXLSX* and *FinalStatisticsXLSX* savers summarize the performance given general statistics, *FinalRankerXLSX* allows comparing the performance of employed algorithms – attained in the last generations – more thoroughly, e.g., by performing statistical comparisons. First, *FinalRankerXLSX* requires selecting a “special” key whose values will “compete” one against another. Typically, one will want to use a key dedicated to the employed method (e.g., “ALGORITHM” in the example being discussed now) so that its values, i.e., concrete algorithms, may be tested against each other. It is precisely why this key was provided via the respective constructor in Listing 35. Regarding the requirements, *FinalRankerXLSX* can be coupled with settings of

FSE0						Wins matrix		Ties matrix		Ranks			TSTUDENT	
GENERATIONS	PS	ALGORITHM	PENALTY	REPAIR	Average	PENALTY	REPAIR	1	2	Average	PENALTY	REPAIR		
													50	100
50	PS	ALGORITHM	100	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	9.68398E-67	9.68398E-67		
		PENALTY	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	1.54362E-82	1.54362E-82		
		REPAIR	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	2	1.62921E-82	1.62921E-82		
		ALGORITHM	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	1.62921E-82	1.62921E-82		
		PENALTY	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	2	9.68398E-67	9.68398E-67		
		REPAIR	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	9.68398E-67	9.68398E-67		
100	PS	ALGORITHM	100	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	2.1375E-57	2.1375E-57		
		PENALTY	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	2.1375E-57	2.1375E-57		
		REPAIR	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	2	4.20791E-58	4.20791E-58		
		ALGORITHM	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	4.20791E-58	4.20791E-58		
		PENALTY	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	2	6.68578E-51	6.68578E-51		
		REPAIR	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	6.68578E-51	6.68578E-51		
100	PS	ALGORITHM	100	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	7.16079E-47	7.16079E-47		
		PENALTY	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	7.16079E-47	7.16079E-47		
		REPAIR	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	2	1.58637E-40	1.58637E-40		
		ALGORITHM	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	1.58637E-40	1.58637E-40		
		PENALTY	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	2	1.58637E-40	1.58637E-40		
		REPAIR	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	1	1.58637E-40	1.58637E-40		

Figure 14: Example result generated by FinalRankerXLSX (fixed items = 100; fixed capacity = 100; compared keys = GENERATIONS, PS, ALGORITHM)

dimensionality of a least 2, and – which is apparent – these settings must include the selected key in their “compared” key sets (i.e. if the dimensionality is less than two or there is no “ALGORITHM” key – in this example – among the compared ones, the saver will not be coupled with the crossed setting).

Figure 14 illustrates the example results for the same crossed setting that was discussed previously. Also, as with the remaining savers, the per-indicator results are kept in separate tabs. Further, the resulting file name will be: string representation of the scenario + “_ranker.key” + selected special key + (optionally) names of the specified statistical tests (will be explained later) + _MD.xlsx (M denotes the number of objectives).

FinalRankerXLSX allows for comparing the algorithm’s performance given one key. For instance, consider Figure 14. The left side of the table consists of all possible crossed scenarios – however, no matter the order of provided keys, the “special” key will always be pushed to the right. Here, the ALGORITHM is last in the order. Further, the special key is also used in the header. This way, the values (algorithms) can be directly compared against one another. The comparison is, however, not performed by inspecting the statistics aggregating the test runs. Instead, it is more thorough and compares the performances attained in all test runs, viewed as a vector. In short, the comparison of one algorithm (row) against another (column) is based on comparing their performances attained in the last generations in all test runs (aggregated in a vector – for each algorithm).

FinalRankerXLSX provides the so-called “wins matrix”, “ties matrix”, “ranks”, and an optional section related to statistical tests. Regarding wins matrix, it reveals in how many of the test runs one method (row) was better than another (column). Note that (i) the comparison is made by inspecting the results attained in consecutive test runs one by one (which is essential to ensure fair comparison). Also, (ii) the saver can be supplied with the equality threshold – the maximum absolute difference between the compared scores that makes them considered equal. Additionally, (iii) the saver considers the performance indicator’s preference direction when making the judgments. Finally, (iv) comparisons of an algorithm with itself are avoided. All (i)-(iv) points are common to all the table segments. Regarding (ii), the ties are reported in the following table segment: “ties matrix”. As for the example interpretation of the results, the table presented in Figure 14 demonstrates that

the REPAIR method outperformed its PENALTY counterpart (100 wins for all scenarios; no ties).

The following table segment concerns the so-called ranks. Imagine, e.g., there are 5 methods compared (instead of two like in this illustrative example). Also, assume that we want to compare their performance given the results they attained in the first test run. Finally, assume that – given the first test run – we want to sort the methods according to their attained scores, i.e., we want to build a ranking. It is assumed that the first method will be assigned a rank of 1, the second of 2, and so on. In case of a tie (the interpretation can be controlled by specifying the threshold for comparison), the ranks are equally redistributed over the equal performance (naturally, such defined comparison relation is not transitive, which raises some issues; in this implementation, the scores are sorted first; then, the equality is checked by comparing subsequent pairs, determining this way a complete segment of scores that are considered “equal” – but the first score in the segment may fail the comparison test when compared with the one; nonetheless, it is recommended not to adjust the comparison threshold – i.e., keep it 0 – when working with doubles). Overall, the “ranks” segment illustrates how many times different ranks were attained across all test runs. For instance, Figure 14 reveals that the REPAIR method was always the best performer, while PENALTY was always placed second. Further, the table also provides information on the average rank attained.

Finally, the table can be extended by auxiliary sections related to statistical comparison. Specifically, FinalRankerXLSX can be supplied with optional tests upon creation (as presented in Listing 35, where FinalRankerXLSX is coupled with TStudent test). These tests have to implement the ITest interface (statistics.test in the Utils module). The central method is here Double getPValue(double[] s1, double[] s2) throws Exception; that is supposed to return p -value given two input samples (that are of equal length). In the initial release of JECDM, only three tests (classes) are provided: TStudent, MannWhitneyU, WilcoxonSignedRank. However, implementing ITest is straightforward, so one may create one’s test when needed. Each test coupled with FinalRankerXLSX will have a dedicated table segment. These segments will be appended from the right side. For instance, the table in Figure 14 has one extra segment: TSTUDENT. The values provided are the p -values calculated

using these statistical tests when comparing two algorithms' performances attained in test runs (two double vectors). In this example, the p -values are extremely close to zero, which is a good sign that one algorithm performs differently than the other (however, one always has to ensure that a particular test is a reasonable choice given some specific experimentation context).

5. Use case #2: evolutionary methods for multi-objective optimization [T]

Source package: `t1_t10.t5_experimentation_module.t3_emo_experiment`

This tutorial showcases how to employ the experimentation module to test various algorithms for evolutionary multi-objective optimization in practice. Note that the test is very generic and, thus, is not oriented on revealing some interesting phenomena. In turn, it serves as a baseline, a foundation for creating experiments. The codes are straightforward adaptations of those presented in Sections 3, 4.1, and 4.2. Consequently, they will not be thoroughly inspected here. Note that creating the global data container and per-scenario/trial factories is moved here to an auxiliary *Utils* class. The central method is here *Containers.getContainers()*, and it returns these three essential components wrapped in *Containers* object (the executors can be explicitly parameterized by passing this object). Regarding the primary characteristics of this experimental design, these are as follows:

- The experiment involves three properties (keys): ALGORITHM, PROBLEM, and OBJECTIVES.
- As for the problems: DTLZ1-4 and WFG1-4 are considered (WFG1 with the bias of 0.2 is utilized).
- The considered numbers of objectives M are 2, 3, 4, and 5.
- The generation limits depend on the scenario's problem and the number of objectives. They are arbitrarily set as $400 + 100(M - 1)$ for DTLZ1, $200 + 50(M - 1)$ for DTLZ2/4, $1000 + 250(M - 1)$ for DTLZ3, $1000 + 200(M - 1)$ for WFG1, and $400 + 100(M - 1)$ for WFG2-4.
- Regarding the algorithms, four methods are employed: NSGA, NSGA-II, NSGA-III, and MOEA/D. These algorithms are set to update their knowledge of the objective space bounds dynamically. Further, their individual parameterizations are as follows:
 - NSGA: Employs the threshold of 0.1 for the niching procedure.
 - NSGA-II: Uses the default parameterization.
 - NSGA-III: Employs the original scalarizing functions whose reference points are generated using the Das and Dennis' method. Also, ties when making assignments are resolved randomly.

- MOEA/D: Employs PBI functions with a penalty factor of 5.0. Their reference points are also generated using the Das and Dennis' method. Further, their similarity is quantified by the Euclidean distance between these points, and the neighborhood size is set to 10.

- The population size of MOEA/D and NSGA-III cannot be freely set if the scalarizing functions are derived via Das and Dennis' method. Thus, they dictate the population size for the remaining methods for a fair comparison. These sizes depend on the number of objectives: 30 for $M = 2$ (the number of cuts for Das and Dennis' method = 29), 66 for $M = 3$ (10 cuts), 120 for $M = 4$ (7 cuts), and 210 for $M = 5$ (6 cuts).
- Four performance indicators are employed to assess the methods: GD, IGD, HV, and an indicator that measures the execution time (note that the last indicator returns the time measured by a method itself when executing the phases; thus, it obviously excludes the time related to managing the experiment, etc.). Regarding GD and IGD, the reference points are pre-constructed and are common to all methods, given that the problem has been tackled. For this reason, random Pareto optimal points are drawn, and such sets are arbitrarily set to $population_size \cdot 2$ (naturally, one may wish to adapt the assessments to one's own needs; this is just a generic example). Further, regarding HV, the reference point – in the normalized space – is set to 1.1^M .

This experiment executes algorithms $4 \cdot 8 \cdot 4 \cdot 100 = 12800$ times in various contexts, which can be considered a significant number. Thus, one may expect the experimentation time to be much longer than when dealing with the knapsack problem. Indeed, the *ExperimentPerformer* reports the elapsed time of around 2 hours (run on 20 threads on AMD Threadripper 1950X; see the summary in Figure 15). Note that, however, a significant part of this time passed was making measurements (e.g., application of HV in 5 dimensions may be time-consuming). For the reader's convenience, all the result files are already supplied with this document in *emo_test.zip* bundle (around 350 MB).

```

THE SUMMARY OF THE EXECUTION PROCESS
Started = [3.12.2024 17:58:14:559]
Ended = [3.12.2024 21:13:2:453]
Took = [days = 0, hours = 3, minutes = 14, seconds = 47, millis = 893]
Termination due to exception = false
Total number of scenarios = 128
Successfully completed scenarios = 128 (may include cases where not all trials were completed)
Terminated scenarios (due to exception) = 0
Skipped scenarios (due to being disabled) = 0
Successfully completed trials (in total) = 12800
Terminated trials (due to exception; in total) = 0
Skipped trials (due to being disabled; in total) = 0

```

Figure 15: Summary of the execution process (*a posteriori* methods)

Note that the final results obtained via *ExperimentPerformer* and – used as post-processing tools – *ScenarioSummarizer* nad *CrossSummarizer* are rich: 51331 files were created and stored in 130 folders. They occupy around 500 MB of disc space. Thus, it is impractical to discuss all these

IGD					Ranks						WSR			
PROBLEM	DTLZ2	OBJECTIVES	ALGORITHM		1	2	3	4	Average	NSGA	NSGAI	NSGAII	MOEAD	
					2	ALGORITHM	NSGA	0	0	0	100	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18
			NSGAI	0	3	97	0	2.97	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	4.33123E-18	4.20238E-18	4.20238E-18	
			NSGAII	45	54	1	0	1.56	3.83809E-18	4.20238E-18	0.390968643	0.390968643	0.390968643	
			MOEAD	55	43	2	0	1.47	3.83809E-18	4.20238E-18	0.390968643	0.390968643	0.390968643	
			NSGA	0	0	47	53	3.53	0.213884626	0.213884626	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	53	47	3.47	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	22	78	0	0	1.78	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	78	22	0	0	1.22	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	99	1	3.01	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	1	99	3.99	3.95591E-18	3.95591E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	4	96	0	0	1.96	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	96	4	0	0	1.04	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	1.87547E-17	1.87547E-17	1.87547E-17	
			NSGA	0	0	100	0	3	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	100	0	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	0	100	0	0	2	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	100	0	0	0	1	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	34	66	3.66	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	2	96	2	0	2	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	7.4444E-18	7.4444E-18	7.4444E-18	
			NSGAII	96	2	0	0	1.02	3.83809E-18	7.4444E-18	4.46399E-18	4.46399E-18	4.46399E-18	
			MOEAD	0	2	64	34	3.32	7.41164E-05	4.46399E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	11	89	3.89	2.4303E-16	2.4303E-16	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	6	83	11	3.05	2.4303E-16	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	100	0	0	0	1	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	0	94	6	0	2.06	3.83809E-18	1.27476E-17	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	0	100	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	100	0	3	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	84	16	0	0	1.16	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	16	84	0	0	1.84	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.49575E-13	3.49575E-13	3.49575E-13	
			NSGA	0	0	0	100	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	100	0	3	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	57	43	0	0	1.43	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	43	57	0	0	1.57	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	0.012491628	0.012491628	0.012491628	

Figure 16: Selected final results (ranks according to IGD)

HV					Ranks						WSR			
PROBLEM	DTLZ2	OBJECTIVES	ALGORITHM		1	2	3	4	Average	NSGA	NSGAI	NSGAII	MOEAD	
					2	ALGORITHM	NSGA	0	0	0	100	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18
			NSGAI	0	2	98	0	2.98	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	4.20238E-18	4.20238E-18	4.20238E-18	
			NSGAII	36	62	2	0	1.66	3.83809E-18	4.20238E-18	0.390968643	0.390968643	0.390968643	
			MOEAD	64	36	0	0	1.36	3.83809E-18	4.20238E-18	2.12354E-05	2.12354E-05	2.12354E-05	
			NSGA	0	0	82	18	3.18	2.44461E-13	2.44461E-13	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	18	82	3.82	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	2	98	0	0	1.98	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	98	2	0	0	1.02	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	5.68109E-18	5.68109E-18	5.68109E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	100	0	3	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	100	0	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	0	100	0	0	2	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	100	0	0	0	1	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	100	0	3	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	100	0	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	0	100	0	0	2	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	100	0	0	0	1	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	56	44	3.44	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	3	97	0	0	1.97	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	1.09827E-17	1.09827E-17	1.09827E-17	
			NSGAII	97	3	0	0	1.03	3.83809E-18	1.09827E-17	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	0	0	44	56	3.55	0.009866799	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	3	97	3.97	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	4	93	3	2.99	7.90454E-18	7.90454E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	100	0	0	0	1	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	0	96	4	0	2.04	3.83809E-18	1.93185E-17	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGA	0	0	0	100	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	100	0	3	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	21	79	0	0	1.79	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	79	21	0	0	1.21	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.0289E-10	3.0289E-10	3.0289E-10	
			NSGA	0	0	0	100	4	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAI	0	0	100	0	3	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			NSGAII	0	100	0	0	2	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	
			MOEAD	100	0	0	0	1	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	

Figure 17: Selected final results (ranks according to HV)

files in this document. It is left to the reader. However, the results are highly consistent with the general, well-known findings on the employed methods – thus, no thorough revisions are needed. As for example snippets of the results, Figures 16 and 17 present distributions of ranks attained by various methods when applied to DTLZ2 and WFG4 (see FIXED_NONE_COMPARED_PROBLEM_OBJECTIVES_ALGORITHM_ranker_key_ALGORITHM_3D.xlsx file, note that some of the columns and rows were made hidden for these illustrations).

6. Use case #3: interactive evolutionary methods for multi-objective optimization [T]

Source package: *t1_t10.t5_experimentation_module.t4_interactive_emo_experiment*

This tutorial is similar to the one in Section 5 (regarding the problems, or the limits for the number of generations), but it concerns interactive, preference-learning methods: CDEMO, DCEMO, NEMO-0, NEMO-II, and IEMO/D. The setting is as follows:

- There are 10 interactions – for each test run – which are evenly distributed starting from generation no. 1.
- A random pair of solutions for comparison is selected during a single interaction.
- The feedback is constructed using an artificial decision-maker modeled with an L_{∞}^w . **Important note:** Following some food practices in testing interactive methods, this experiment assumes that different weight vectors w are coupled with the artificial decision maker in each trail within one scenario (see, e.g., [1, 2]). This way, the ability to understand various policies can be comprehensively tested. Note that the weights used are pre-defined and common to all methods to ensure fair comparison (see the code comments).
- All algorithms use FRS to decompose the indirect preferences into compatible L_{∞}^w -norms (except for CDEMO and DCEMO that do not incorporate a preference disaggregation technique).
- Assessment of the performance of interactive methods follows different guidelines than for *a posteriori* methods (as the goal is not to construct a fine approximation of the Pareto front). Here, six indicators are used: (1-2) constructed solutions are assessed given the artificial decision maker's model (who plays the role of an oracle during the assessment). Two variants of this indicator are employed. The first (1) quantifies the relevance of the best solution in the population, while the second (2) calculates the average (both are marked later as VMQ-MIN/MEAN). Further, (3) GD is employed to measure how close the constructed populations are to the Pareto front (convergence is still an essential property), (4) execution time in ms is measured, (5) the size of the history of preference elicitation is reported, and (6) notifies about the number of inconsistencies detected (although the models employed in the methods are consistent with the artificial decision maker's model are consistent, FRS can still signal inconsistency if the computational resources are limited and the preference disaggregation task is particularly challenging).

As with the case presented in the preceding Section 5, the experimentation results are rich (96163 files stored in 162 folders, around 896 MB of used disc space), and it again took around

2 hours to complete the processing (see the summary in Figure 18). Therefore, for the reader's convenience, the results files are delivered along this tutorial document in *imo_test.zip* bundle file (around 430 MB).

As with the study on *a posteriori* methods, this section does not thoroughly investigate the results – it would be unpractical. Nonetheless, they are consistent with the general finding on these employed interactive methods. Nonetheless, Figures 19 and 20 present distributions of ranks attained by various methods when applied to DTLZ2 and WFG4 for reader's convenience (see `FIXED_NONE_COMPARED_PROBLEM_OBJECTIVES_ALGORITHM_ranker_key_ALGORITHM_WSR_3D.xlsx` file, note that some of the columns and rows were made hidden for these illustrations).

```
THE SUMMARY OF THE EXECUTION PROCESS
Started = [5.12.2024 9:54:17:564]
Ended = [5.12.2024 11:43:21:765]
Took = [days = 0, hours = 1, minutes = 49, seconds = 4, millis = 200]
Termination due to exception = false
Total number of scenarios = 160
Successfully completed scenarios = 160 (may include cases where not all trials were completed)
Terminated scenarios (due to exception) = 0
Skipped scenarios (due to being disabled) = 0
Successfully completed trials (in total) = 16000
Terminated trials (due to exception; in total) = 0
Skipped trials (due to being disabled; in total) = 0
```

Figure 18: Summary of the execution process (interactive methods)

References

- [1] J. Marquis, E. S. Gel, J. W. Fowler, M. Köksalan, P. Korhonen, and J. Wallenius, "Impact of number of interactions, different interaction patterns, and human inconsistencies on some hybrid evolutionary multiobjective optimization algorithms," *Decision Sciences*, vol. 46, no. 5, pp. 981–1006, 2015.
- [2] M. K. Tomczyk and M. Kadziński, "Decomposition-based interactive evolutionary algorithm for multiple objective optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 320–334, 2020.

VMQ_MIN					Ranks					WSR									
PROBLEM	DTLZZ	OBJECTIVES	ALGORITHM	CDEMO	1	2	3	4	5	Average	CDEMO	DCEMO	NEMOII	NEMOII	ITEMOD				
										14	15	30	34	7	3.05	0.166381191	0.166381191	4.58014E-15	5.262E-06
PROBLEM	DTLZZ	OBJECTIVES	2	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	15	29	21	27	8	2.84	0.166381191	0.166381191	6.91166E-15	0.001251532	0.115711035			
					NEMOII	4	3	6	9	78	4.54	4.59014E-15	6.91166E-15	7.02957E-17	4.84834E-15	0.002383437			
					ITEMOD	45	21	23	9	2	2.02	5.262E-06	0.001251532	7.02957E-17	4.84834E-15	0.002383437			
					CDEMO	22	32	20	21	5	2.55	0.067828825	0.115711035	4.84834E-15	0.002383437	0.002383437			
			3	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	15	10	26	32	17	3.26	0.781945085	0.781945085	3.15236E-08	2.5172E-09	5.78687E-09			
					NEMOII	0	6	13	12	69	4.44	3.19238E-08	9.94728E-08	4.33123E-18	1.39021E-09	2.37167E-10			
					ITEMOD	38	31	19	12	0	2.05	2.5172E-09	1.39021E-09	4.33123E-18	1.39021E-09	2.37167E-10			
					CDEMO	39	33	19	9	0	1.88	5.78687E-09	2.37167E-10	1.23736E-17	0.784586524	0.784586524			
				4	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	7	12	34	34	13	3.34	0.48626553	0.48626553	4.51496E-11	1.15658E-11	1.89883E-13		
						NEMOII	1	0	11	14	74	4.6	4.51496E-11	3.38355E-10	4.07731E-18	4.07731E-18	4.60076E-18		
						ITEMOD	38	42	15	5	0	1.87	1.32623E-12	1.84277E-12	4.60076E-18	4.60076E-18	0.913751986		
						CDEMO	45	37	15	2	1	1.77	1.89883E-13	4.27702E-14	4.60076E-18	0.913751986	0.913751986		
		5			ALGORITHM	DCEMO	10	10	40	35	5	3.15	0.049017321	0.049017321	1.56435E-15	1.15658E-11	1.35165E-13		
						NEMOII	3	13	28	44	12	3.49	0.049017321	1.43442E-14	1.43442E-14	4.22804E-15	4.22804E-15		
						ITEMOD	0	0	5	12	83	4.78	1.56435E-15	1.43442E-14	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18	3.83809E-18		
						CDEMO	36	43	15	6	0	1.91	1.15658E-11	3.19654E-14	3.83809E-18	0.225508741	0.225508741		
			WFG4		OBJECTIVES	2	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	11	14	26	34	15	3.28	0.317875419	0.317875419	2.15204E-08	0.003853496	0.00227691
								NEMOII	11	14	13	6	56	3.82	1.41947E-06	2.15204E-08	3.82544E-09	3.30952E-10	0.003853496
								ITEMOD	32	26	20	15	7	2.39	0.000559842	0.003853496	3.82544E-09	0.208859488	0.208859488
								CDEMO	40	31	13	9	7	2.12	0.000559842	0.00227691	3.30952E-10	0.208859488	0.208859488
				3		ALGORITHM	DCEMO	15	11	32	42	9	3.97	0.012251385	0.012251385	8.53344E-09	6.25007E-13	3.87025E-13	
							NEMOII	3	15	24	36	22	3.59	0.012251385	3.9783E-06	3.9783E-06	1.25659E-13	3.29977E-12	
							ITEMOD	5	3	13	11	68	4.34	8.53344E-09	3.9783E-06	1.27476E-17	1.82071E-17	1.82071E-17	
							CDEMO	41	41	13	4	1	1.83	6.26007E-13	1.25659E-13	1.27476E-17	0.932866444	0.932866444	
	4	ALGORITHM				DCEMO	1	6	24	45	14	3.65	0.406337846	0.406337846	1.77426E-06	1.76754E-17	8.64752E-18		
						NEMOII	4	2	20	7	67	4.31	1.77426E-06	1.13334E-06	1.56973E-17	9.74632E-18	9.74632E-18		
						ITEMOD	41	49	8	1	1	1.72	1.76754E-17	5.68109E-18	1.56973E-17	0.299896999	0.299896999		
						CDEMO	54	40	6	0	1.52	8.64752E-18	6.21747E-18	9.74632E-18	0.299896999	0.299896999			
		5			ALGORITHM	DCEMO	0	4	34	49	13	3.74	0.514683408	0.514683408	5.60125E-07	3.83809E-18	7.4445E-18		
						NEMOII	0	5	30	45	20	3.8	0.514683408	9.35367E-07	4.20238E-18	7.0111E-18	7.0111E-18		
						ITEMOD	3	1	24	5	67	4.32	5.60125E-07	9.35367E-07	1.13152E-17	7.22464E-18	7.22464E-18		
						CDEMO	48	48	4	0	0	1.56	3.83809E-18	4.20238E-18	1.13152E-17	0.595265512	0.595265512		

Figure 19: Selected final results (ranks according to VMQ-MIN)

VMQ_MEAN					Ranks					WSR									
PROBLEM	DTLZZ	OBJECTIVES	ALGORITHM	CDEMO	1	2	3	4	5	Average	CDEMO	DCEMO	NEMOII	NEMOII	ITEMOD				
										19	23	23	27	8	2.82	0.968459277	0.968459277	3.6684E-09	0.155099617
PROBLEM	DTLZZ	OBJECTIVES	2	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	25	19	21	20	15	2.81	0.968459277	0.968459277	4.03563E-08	0.38907263	0.155099617			
					NEMOII	18	7	4	14	57	3.85	3.6684E-09	4.03563E-08	2.65104E-10	2.02831E-10	0.590509505			
					ITEMOD	18	27	28	17	10	2.74	0.155099617	0.38907263	2.65104E-10	2.02831E-10	0.590509505			
					CDEMO	20	24	24	22	10	2.78	0.38311954	0.16956255	2.02831E-10	0.590509505	0.590509505			
			3	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	17	17	15	33	18	3.18	0.753060274	0.753060274	0.003089612	5.9531E-06	8.55066E-06			
					NEMOII	17	19	18	26	20	3.13	0.753060274	0.015133163	2.92429E-05	8.67846E-05	8.67846E-05			
					ITEMOD	15	14	10	11	50	3.67	0.003089612	0.015133163	7.71056E-09	3.17056E-09	3.17056E-09			
					CDEMO	26	19	37	15	3	2.5	5.9531E-06	2.92429E-05	7.71056E-09	3.17056E-09	3.17056E-09			
				4	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	25	31	20	15	9	2.52	8.55066E-06	8.67846E-05	3.17056E-09	0.753060274	0.753060274		
						NEMOII	19	12	19	27	23	3.23	0.845968113	0.845968113	0.001550947	2.88039E-05	3.80653E-08		
						ITEMOD	8	11	34	29	18	3.30	0.001550947	0.002954508	0.002954508	8.2097E-06	6.67846E-10		
						CDEMO	23	9	9	10	49	3.53	0.001550947	0.002954508	3.733E-08	6.68171E-09	0.15569166		
		5			ALGORITHM	DCEMO	26	23	24	20	7	2.59	2.88039E-05	8.2097E-06	3.733E-08	0.15569166	0.15569166		
						NEMOII	24	45	14	14	3	2.27	3.80653E-08	6.67846E-05	6.68171E-09	0.15569166	0.15569166		
						ITEMOD	17	18	29	26	10	2.94	0.017919048	0.017919048	9.26209E-06	0.14022632	0.00032468		
						CDEMO	13	16	21	30	20	3.28	0.017919048	0.00223337	0.00223337	0.00223337	2.80346E-06		
			WFG4		OBJECTIVES	2	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	20	9	5	11	55	3.72	9.26209E-06	0.00022337	2.72802E-08	1.12213E-09	0.02863955
								NEMOII	23	24	26	18	9	2.66	0.014022632	0.00022337	2.72802E-08	0.02863955	0.02863955
								ITEMOD	27	33	19	15	6	2.4	0.00032468	2.80346E-06	1.12213E-09	0.02863955	0.02863955
								CDEMO	16	25	23	27	9	2.88	0.656129655	0.656129655	1.89648E-10	0.21136126	0.08150016
				3		ALGORITHM	DCEMO	19	16	26	28	11	2.96	1.89648E-10	1.07492E-09	1.07492E-09	0.007061552	0.00217476	
							NEMOII	11	6	10	8	65	4.1	1.89648E-10	1.07492E-09	5.36528E-12	3.49575E-13	3.49575E-13	
							ITEMOD	27	21	20	24	8	2.65	0.21136126	0.007061552	5.36528E-12	3.49575E-13	3.49575E-13	
							CDEMO	27	32	21	13	7	2.41	0.008150016	0.00217476	3.49575E-13	0.317875419	0.317875419	
	4	ALGORITHM				DCEMO	10	16	31	27	16	3.23	0.202699807	0.202699807	0.000857743	4.0694E-05	2.87137E-07		
						NEMOII	17	16	15	31	21	3.23	0.202699807	0.00124257	0.00124257	6.6819E-07	1.02023E-11		
						ITEMOD	13	12	13	5	57	3.81	0.000857743	0.00124257	3.38355E-10	1.00235E-11	0.327973726		
						CDEMO	25	32	21	17	5	2.45	4.0694E-05	6.6819E-07	3.38355E-10	0.327973726	0.327973726		
		5			ALGORITHM	DCEMO	35	24	20	20	1	2.28	2.87137E-07	1.02084E-06	1.00235E-11	0.327973726	0.327973726		
						NEMOII	12	16	24	24	24	3.32	0.364936595	0.364936595	0.039937081	2.66564E-05	1.73388E-10		
						ITEMOD	4	11	25	35	25	3.66	0.039937081	0.054819458	0.054819458	3.16182E-09	3.32209E-13		
						CDEMO	21	10	16	10	43	3.44	0.039937081	0.054819458	2.71084E-06	1.5646E-08	1.5646E-08		
				5	ALGORITHM	DCEMO	29	26	19	22	4	2.46	2.66564E-05	3.10492E-09	2.71084E-06	1.5646E-08	0.059770486		
						NEMOII	34	37	16	9	4	2.12	1.73388E-10	3.32209E-13	1.5646E-08	0.059770486	0.059770486		
						ITEMOD	11	5	26	35	23	3.54	0.768775651	0.768775651	0.090384113	2.16907E-10	5.13992E-10		
						CDEMO	5	17	21	41	16	3.46	0.768775651	0.1531234	0.1531234	1.35316E-10	1.25339E-10		

Figure 20: Selected final results (ranks according to VMQ-MEAN)